

AN AMERICAN SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL

Zien Journal

of

Social Sciences and Humanities

VOLUME 9, SEPTEMBER, 2024

Vol. 9 (2024): ZJSSH

Articles

1. [Features of the Formation of a System of Social and Value Orientations of Women](#)
1-3
Seitova Zukhrakhon Pirzhanovna, Zhamilova Gulbahar
2. [Educational Pedagogy and Life Laws Method](#)
4-8
Orasta Davronova
3. [The legal rules regulating the end-of-service gratuity according to Iraqi Legislation](#)
9-15
Zeyad Tareq Ibrahim
4. [The Golden Ratio in the Quran](#)
16-21
M.M. Aripov, M.A. Mardankulova, U.M. Oripova
5. [Old and new challenges and threats in Algerian political life](#)
22-24
Rasulov Otabek Abdulazizovich
6. [Professional and Personal Characteristics of Leadership Individually Leadership](#)
25-26
Elmurodov Ulug'bek Yusup og'li
7. [The issues of spiritual growth, morality and ethics in society are in the works of our enlightened scholars](#)
27-28
Major Akhmedov Murodjon Mahmudovich, Israilova Shakhnoza Tolkinovna
8. [The first swallow of the East](#)
29-30
Sharipova Shahlo Kholikulovna
9. [Psychology of self-development](#)
31-33
Sadirxonova Shoista Abidjanova
10. [Environmental sensing and its role in achieving strategic agility Analytical descriptive research in the Iraqi South Oil Company](#)
34-44
Mustafa Sabah Hlehel, Tariq Kazem Shalaka

11. Difficulties in Mastering English Grammar Faced by Secondary School Students' (Fifth Islamic Grade) from teachers' perspective

45-56

Omar Mahmood Mustafa AL-Okiedy

12. Interpretation of works in modern uzbek dramaturgy in the form of the image of contemporaries

57-59

Navro'za Qodirjonava Ashirmurodovna

13. Teenagers Psychology in Young Wrestlers

60-62

Bekov Dilshod Haytboyevich

14. Formation of legal consciousness among young people

63-66

Captain Tursunov Alisher Qahramonovich

15. Psycholinguistic, ethno-sociocultural aspects as basis of intercultural communication

67-68

Mavlonova Oybachin Sheraliyevna

16. The concept of heroism and its representation in the novel "The Old Man and The Sea"

69-71

Sobirova Nurkhon Barot kizi

17. Review of the Issue of Faith (Iman) In the Works of Hakim Tirmidhi

72-75

Zafar Fakhriddinov

Features Of the Formation of a System of Social and Value Orientations of Women

Seitova Zukhrakhon Pirzhanovna

Associate Professor, PhD, Nukus state pedagogical institute named after Ajiniyaz
Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan

Zhamilova Gulbahar

Lecturer, Nukus state pedagogical institute named after Ajiniyaz
Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan

Abstract: In the article, the author touches on the issues of social and value targeting women. With the expansion of the role of women in social production, there is a process of qualitative change on the part of all strata of society towards the female factor. This new social state of women is facilitated by the purposeful policy of our young state to empower women in the public life of the country. That women's rights are primarily guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Key words: Strategy, social orientation, value orientations, subject.

In 2016-2019, Uzbekistan implemented fundamental reforms affecting almost all spheres of society and all categories of citizens living in the country. On the basis of the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, special attention was paid to such priority areas as improving the system of state and social construction, ensuring the rule of law and further reforming the judicial and legal system, development and liberalization of the national economy, strengthening the social sphere, ensuring security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, implementing an effective foreign policy.

With the expansion of the role of women in social production, there is a process of qualitative change on the part of all strata of society towards the female factor. This new social state of women is facilitated by the purposeful policy of our young state to empower women in the public life of the country. Women's rights are primarily guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which, in particular, states that men and women have not only equal rights and freedoms, but equal opportunities for their realization. Of fundamental importance for the understanding of women's rights is the fact that the generally recognized principles and norms of international law are an integral part of the legal system of our society [5.- No. 137].

"A woman is a ruler and ruler in love, is a mighty, affectionate and gentle force that brings up a man," wrote V.A. Sukhomlinsky. [9.-C.277].

The state of society, the level of its development and potential opportunities are largely determined by the position of women. In turn, the changes taking place in society are reflected in the system of values of women, their social value orientations. Value orientations, like social values themselves, being in general a product of human activity, at the same time are directly related to socio-economic, social - the political nature of society and the objective conditions of objective activity, as well as with social attitudes correlated with the integrity of the way of life, in comparison with attitudes towards private social objects and situations, individual actions. They are a reflection of fundamental interests, and express the subjective social position of people, their worldview and moral principles. The formation of a system of value orientations means the formation of an individual as an active subject of social reality.

In a society consisting of men and women with a clearly expressed specificity of their values, the study of the processes of formation and dynamics of women's value orientations is a permanently urgent task. Another side of the relevance of the study is the emergence of new problems in the relationship between women and society, associated with the formation of market relations in modern society, a change in social and cultural priorities.

An important and fairly independent place in the system of social relations is occupied by the social value orientations of women. The specificity of social value orientations is determined by the place they

occupy among other value orientations. However, the analysis of the formation of social value orientations is impossible without deep penetration into the specifics of social, social relationships. Therefore, before proceeding to consider the system of social orientations of women, it is necessary to analyze the concept of "social relations".

In the literature, there are two main positions on the issue of social relations. The first group of authors identifies social relations with public ones [7.-1987]. The second group considers social relations as specific in the system of social relations, while understanding their specificity in different ways. [8.-1873] When considering the most essential specific features social relations, it is necessary to bear in mind the fact that, firstly, communities and individuals act as the subjects of these relations, and individuals are carriers of social qualities, ultimately determined by their place in the systems of production, distribution, consumption and management; secondly, it is the relationship of equality and inequality in the position of people and groups in society: thirdly, it is the relationship of individuals, social communities and groups, mediated by elements of the environment - things, objects, tools.

However, all of the above points, although they characterize social relations from various angles, still do not provide sufficient grounds to distinguish them among other types of social relations. The main distinguishing feature of social relations is that these are relations between social subjects as wholes, in contrast, for example, from political relations, where the subject acts with only one side of it. All other social relations are integrated into social ones to the extent that they reflect the interaction of subjects as wholes.

Since social relations are relations "between groups of people occupying different positions in society, taking unequal participation in its economic and spiritual life, differing not only in the level, but also in the source of their income, the structure of personal consumption, lifestyle, level of personal development, type public consciousness" insofar as these differences are recorded in social value orientations. In other words, social value orientations reflect the qualitative uniqueness of the systemic subjects of social relations, regardless of the field of activity of these subjects.

Thus, speaking about the study of the social value orientations of certain social subjects, we assume the study of social subjects in all the variety of their external and internal connections, including the study of various aspects of their life - socio-political, socio-economic, sociocultural, etc. As you know, the basis of human activity, including social, is his needs, both material and spiritual. All human activity is aimed at satisfying these needs.

Need acts as a stimulus for human activity. The realization of activity is the first prerequisite for the existence of a social subject. In view of the objective dependence of a person on the social environment, there is a relationship between what is objectively necessary for him to function in the political or economic sphere, and what is really at his disposal. Reflected in the mind of a person sometimes on an unconscious level, need prompts him to take active action to satisfy it. On this path, several levels of need development can be distinguished: a state of dissatisfaction, when there is a readiness for action, but without an objective orientation (unconscious need); awareness of the need; awareness of the way to satisfy the need. From the level of objective need, the practical manifestation of necessity, a transition is made to the reflection of this need in consciousness, to the ideal urge of the subject to the inner "image" of the necessary. There is an awareness and experience of the objective need for the form of emotions and the need for volitional actions.

Understanding social need and activity as a cause and effect, respectively, helps to reveal the mechanism of the transition of a need into an activity, in the process of which this need is satisfied.

However, it should be borne in mind that the connection between need and activity is so dialectical that it will be more accurate to speak of their interdependence. To become an active force, a social need must be actualized, revealed as significant, internally related to the real object. At the same time, the need to satisfy the need generates a certain activity aimed at its satisfaction, i.e. generates social interest.

It is on this basis that you can conduct a conversation and about the interests of women, bearing in mind those features that characterize them, on the one hand, as something in common, on the other, as distinguishing them from other social groups and communities. Interests, as interpreted by A.G. Zdravomyslov and A.G. Khanipov, serve as a source of development for subjects of social action, assert their subjectivity, their interest, their line of behavior in the objective result of action.

Thus, despite the integral nature of interest as a social phenomenon, it is quite possible to speak about the features of social interests and needs in the same way as we talked about the features of social relations. The

social interests of women are primarily determined by their place and role in the social structure, their participation in social life. At the same time, the social interests of women to a certain extent reflect social relations in society as a whole, determine in a concentrated form the social position of women as one of the subjects of social development, the totality of their social ties with other groups of society. As you know, women are a socio-demographic group, distinguished on the basis of a set of sexual (biological) characteristics, characteristics of social status and, due to both, socio-psychological properties.

The socio-psychological characteristics of women and their social status are of a socio-historical nature and depend on the social system and the level of culture (as well as the regularities of socialization inherent in a given society, stereotypes of thinking). The role of women as a social group especially increases during periods of social change, which mark the transition from one system of values, from one model of social development to another. But, as a rule, the socio-political radicalism of women is expressed mainly in value judgments, less in real actions. In the process of determining the significance of objects and phenomena of social life, a person, including a woman, realizes the degree of their correspondence their interests and needs. In the mind of a woman, a specific state arises, which can be characterized as a social attitude towards the performance of certain activities aimed at realizing social interest. Social attitudes represent a stable position of the individual in a specific social (socio-political or socio-economic) situation, due to the great importance and as a result of the frequent repetition of current social attitudes, their identification, consolidation and formation of a relatively holistic and stable system is carried out. This system is the social value orientations of women.

Social orientations have characteristic features. First, all of them, in one way or another, express the nature of a person's orientation towards the reproduction and development of their social qualities. Secondly, they are all implemented in the social sphere, which includes working and living conditions, health protection, opportunities for study and leisure, and etc. Women act as not only an object, but also a subject of historical action, with varying degrees of activity participating in social processes, in public life, in the spheres of production, politics, culture. Women as a socio-demographic community have their own specific characteristics associated with the characteristics of gender and psychology and ultimately determined by the role of the mother children, style of role behavior. Among the characteristics determined by gender, as already mentioned, should be attributed to the stable attitude of women to such a socially significant function as motherhood, and hence to family, children. All this sets a strictly normative orientation for each link in the structure of formation social value orientations of women: needs, interests, attitudes, value orientations.

Thus, taking into account the analysis of the nature of the social, as well as the specifics of women as a special social group, their social value orientations can be defined as a system of fixed attitudes, in which their social behavior and personal attitude to the needs and interests of society as a certain qualitative integrity and to their own social status.

References:

1. Decree of the President of February 7, 2017 No. 4947.
2. Resolution of the President of March 7, 2019 No. 4235.
3. Laws No. 561 and 562 of September 2, 2019.
4. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 192 dated March 30, 2020.
5. Bekmuradov M.B., Ubaydullaeva P.A. What is stopping an Uzbek woman? // People's word. No. 137. July 3, 2004. <http://www.centrasia.ru>.
6. Giddens E. Basic problems of social theory: action, structure and contradiction in social analysis / E. Giddens // Social and humanitarian sciences. Domestic and foreign literature. Ser.7. Literary criticism: RZh / RAN.INION.-M., 1996.-№11.-P.22-51.
7. Gidnev P. Philosophy and social cognition. M. 1987; Drozdov A.V. On the problem of social relations, M. 1989.
8. Orlov L.V. Social relations. L. 1873.
9. Sukhomlinsky V.A. How to bring up a real person. Mn. 1978.

EDUCATIONAL PEDAGOGY AND LIFE LAWS METHOD

Orasta Davronova

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute
Faculty of Pedagogy, Department of Physics and Astronomy
F A1-22 group 3rd stage student

Abstract: In the article, the author touches on the issues of social and value targeting women. With the expansion of the role of women in social production, there is a process of qualitative change on the part of all strata of society towards the female factor. This new social state of women is facilitated by the purposeful policy of our young state to empower women in the public life of the country. That women's rights are primarily guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Key words: Strategy, social orientation, value orientations, subject.

The only rational way to teach a person something is to show a personal example...
Albert Enshteyn

Annotation. The article will talk about the need to begin to influence the formation of a child's worldview in infancy. You can also read the reviews of industry scientists on this topic and get motivated.

Keywords: education, upbringing, worldview, child development, speech, speech development, stimulus.

Raising a child from infancy is one of the most difficult tasks in the world, but there is no generally accepted successful educational program for parents. So, the only way to do this is to use his personal actions as an opportunity, through the study of Simple Ways and everyday activities to stimulate the development of the brain of the child. The child learns everything in the process of growing up, mainly from the adults around him. Take a lesson from them, imitating them, and gain vital experience. Now, if you yourself are rude and mischievous-he, you will make a mistake if you think that your child is brought up with beautiful manners and manners. If you smoke or drink on your own-he says, I will return your child from these bad ills, then your hopes and actions are fraught. Do not be distracted by the fact that you yourself are a liar or a deceiver, waiting for honesty and trustworthiness from your child.

Хар бир ишни
тадрижийлик билан
амалга ошириш
мақсадга мувофиқдир.

Болани бирор-бир
ютуққа эришишида,
натижани кўришга
шўшмаслик керак.

Фарзандни тарбия
қилганда, унинг ёши ва
савиясини инобатга
олиш муҳим.

For example, up to two years old they are brought up only with sweet words, through manipulation. Until the age of five, the child learns the environment, acquires basic knowledge in this age range. During this

period, it will be necessary for us to try to become an example from a more practical point of view, to create a healthy family environment.

Масару Ибука

Япониялик муҳандис ва
тадбиркор, “Sony”
корпорациясининг
асосчиларидан бири, ёш
болаларни тарбиялаш ва
ўқитиш бўйича кашшоф
тушунчаларни яратувчиси.
Болаларнинг эрта
ривожланиши бўйича
тавсиялар жамланмаси
саналган “Учдан кейин кеч”
таниқли бестселлери
муаллифи.

One of the co-founders of Sony, Masaru Ibuka, put forward the idea of looking at each child as if he were looking at the future genius in his" late after three "work, to represent him to the reader that if he is divided into genius-specific attitudes, he can become a tremendous talent when the infant grows up. In fact, a genius is hidden in every child. And who is his adult is the product of the attitude and upbringing of an adult. Only in this regard should not be delayed.

Наполеон Банопард

1769 йил 15 август - 1821 йил 5
май, француз қўмондони ва
сиёсий етакчиси

Томас Алва Эдисон

1847 йил 11 февраль -1931 йил
18-октабр Машхур америкалик
ихтирочи

"I will reveal to you the secret of amazing changes!says Joe Vitale in his work "four steps towards happiness". Like the same, we want to reveal secrets that have caused some successful changes. For example, the French emperor Napoleon Banopard xali, at a very young age, said: "Sir, stand up, great things are waiting for you!"as long as they woke up. Either The fact that when the great inventor Thomas Edison was expelled from school, his mother told him that the school administration had been guided by his unique

talent, which distinguished him from others, and that the child had been asked to continue studying at home temporarily until they reached Thomas, that he would not go to school, and that he was able to.

Боланинг яширин
имкониятлари

Эрта тажрибанинг таъсири

Гўдак учун фойдали
омиллар

Тарбия қоидалари

Нимадан чегараламаслик
керак?

In the work "late after three" by the author of Masaru Ibuka, the factors that manifest in the formation of the child's Worldview are singled out separately. Taking into account this, it is noted that it is also necessary to give an incentive to its current state. In addition, during the formation of the child's worldview in the course of this work, it is recommended to follow the following:

1. Support and encouragement of the child. The sounds that the babies make and their gestures do not always represent a clear goal, that is, every time they cry, the belly will not be hungry. But such a method is their only form of communication. Experts who are engaged in the development of children at an early age argue that it is necessary to support and encourage children by paying attention to such unusual behavior and tone of voice and to perceive it as a real conversation. Parents should respond to the child's sounds, signals and actions and communicate with him throughout the day.

The words that a child hears before the age of two, and basically their number, constitute the volume of vocabulary at this age, and subsequently affect the development of his or her reading abilities. It is necessary to take the child seriously and stimulate it.

2. To develop his speech, give him a book reading. Perhaps young children have not yet learned to speak or read, but they are actually ready to learn from birth. In the three-month period, they distinguish each sound that is used in different languages.

Every time a child is read something aloud, his speech and language skills are achieved to progress. During reading, the child can show pictures in the book and ask questions about the story and its characters. It helps the child develop speech and language skills. Reading books to young children not only helps to learn new words and remember them, but also teaches love for reading books. Remember, leaders are those who read and read a lot at the same time, so why not start this process as soon as possible? "If you want your children to be smart, tell them to read fairy tales," said Albert Enshteyn, a great scientist, the inventor of a number of universal physical laws. If you want them to be smarter, then read more fairy tales."..

3. Allocate also minutes for training on the agenda. For small children, each of the daily movements by adults is educational. Whether it's a bath, laundry, cooking or completing assignments - all these actions are a great opportunity to learn. During certain actions, it is necessary to say out loud what is being done in order for the child to perform speech activities. For example, to teach mathematics, it is possible to lay the foundation for his knowledge of physics and chemistry by counting and sorting clothes in the closet, to name

-
10. Собитова М. Э. Способы заинтересовать учащихся первого класса на уроке //Студенческий. – 2021. – №. 1-3. – С. 17-18.
 11. Ziyonet – таълим портали.

The legal rules regulating the end-of-service gratuity according to Iraqi Legislation

Zeyad Tareq Ibrahim
University of Samarra
Email : zeyad.albaitar@uosamarra.edu.iq

Abstract: Labor laws determine the cases of termination of the work association. These legislations guarantee a retirement salary to the worker whose service is terminated, provided that he is protected and covered by social security, meaning that he fulfills the legal requirements, which include the payment of pension contributions. However, there are exceptional cases in which they expire. The work relationship, whether in collective or individual labor contracts, without those contracts fulfilling the legal requirements, whether in terms of years of service, Or in terms of collecting pension contributions during the period of his service or work with the employer, especially if he is not protected or covered by social security, in this case the person is entitled to a reward known as the end-of-service gratuity , as it has been approved to protect and compensate him and his family for his loss of work and the possibility of He will have not obtaining another job opportunity after the end of his service, especially if he is old, so we will try to explain the issue from various aspects in accordance with the Iraqi legislation in force.

Key words: Labor laws, work association

Introduction

Labor laws determine the cases of termination of the work association. These legislations guarantee a retirement salary to the worker whose service is terminated, provided that he is protected and covered by social security, meaning that he fulfills the legal requirements, which include the payment of pension contributions. However, there are exceptional cases in which they expire. The work relationship, whether in collective or individual labor contracts, without those contracts fulfilling the legal requirements, whether in terms of years of service, Or in terms of collecting pension contributions during the period of his service or work with the employer, especially if he is not protected or covered by social security, in this case the person is entitled to a reward known as the end-of-service gratuity , as it has been approved to protect and compensate him and his family for his loss of work and the possibility of He will have not obtaining another job opportunity after the end of his service, especially if he is old, so we will try to explain the issue from various aspects in accordance with the Iraqi legislation in force.

Research division

Proceeding from the fact that social security has become one of the basic rights of the worker, which is stipulated in many constitutions and different laws, especially for people who do not have a pension salary, it has become necessary to study the nature of those rewards and the extent of their entitlement and the people covered by them, so we have divided this research into three basic chapters:

The first chapter we will talk about the definition of end-of-service gratuity, as it is divided into two basic sections dealing with the first section, the legal concept of end-of-service gratuity, while addressing the second section distinguishing end-of-service gratuity from other rewards and wages, and the second chapter We have devoted it to clarifying the cases of termination of service in the various Iraqi legislation, where the first section dealt with the case of the termination of the contract by a unilateral will and the second section the case of the termination of the contract due to the impossibility of final implementation, while the third section dealt with the hypothesis of the expiry of the fixed-term contract. As for the third chapter, it deals with the legal regulation of the end-of-service gratuity, then we conclude the research with the most important results, and we put the appropriate recommendations for them.

Chapter One

Definition of end of service gratuity

The insured worker deserves end-of-service gratuity in accordance with the law and regardless of the cases of termination of the work contract, as the insured worker may not meet the conditions set by the law for entitlement to the retirement salary, so the various laws have surrounded the worker with many guarantees and rights, perhaps the most prominent of which is the end-of-service gratuity which is paid once within the terms determined by law, as it is considered as compensation to the worker for the end of his service, Therefore, we will divide this chapter into two sections that we deal with in the first section, a statement of the legal concept of end-of-service gratuity, while the second section will address cases that may be similar to that reward and the differences between them, in accordance with the different Iraqi legislation.

First Section

Legal concept of end of service gratuity

Defining the legal concept requires a statement of what is meant by end-of-service gratuity, which requires its definition, with an indication of the legal nature of it according to its characteristics, and as dealt with by the various Iraqi legislations.

Definition of end-of-service gratuity According to the legal concept, labor and social security legislation almost combines a common definition of end-of-service gratuity, despite the disparity in terms and expressions, in (it is a monetary amount to which the worker is entitled in the event of the end of his service if he is not covered by social security), The Retirement and Social Security for Workers Law No. 39 of 1971 defined it (as the amount that the institution pays to the insured in the absence of the conditions for his entitlement to the pension or in other cases stipulated by the law) (1). The Unified Retirement Law defined it as (a sum of money paid to an employee who has been retired in accordance with the law). (2)

Second section

Distinguish the end-of-service gratuity

Most of the legal legislations agree that the end-of-service gratuity is not considered compensation, because its payment is not due to an error committed by the employer towards the worker in order for him to be obligated to pay it to him, and the worker who is entitled to it was not harmed by the end of his work so that he can claim the owner Compensation work, as the legal legislation determines that the worker is entitled to end-of-service gratuity even in the event of no fault of the employer, as is the case with the termination of the work contract by the expiry of its term. Or because of the worker's inability to work or because of his death, just as the worker is entitled to end-of-service gratuity without the need to prove that he sustained damage as a result of the termination of his contract, even if it is proven that he benefited from this termination by joining him to work for which he receives a wage in excess of what he was receiving under Work contract that has expired. An opinion in the judiciary tends to consider the end-of-service gratuity an additional wage imposed by law on the employer at the end of the contract, and this results in the award being subject to all provisions related to wages, except in cases where an express provision is stated that contradicts these provisions, then the end-of-service gratuity The obligation of the direct source of the law and its cause is the services provided by the worker as a result of the contract concluded between him and the employer (3), in this description it is considered a kind of overtime (4) Another opinion in the jurisprudence goes that end-of-service gratuity is closer to a guarantee than to a deferred wage, in the end the legal legislation has settled that end-of-service gratuity is not a kind of wages, because it is not subject to the regulations on salaries and wages Unless the law expressly provides for this (5) In view of the multiplicity of laws dealing with the organization of the work contract and the diversity of protection methods for the worker, cases have emerged that are similar to the end-of-service gratuity in some aspects, but differ from them in other aspects, such as the retirement salary, work injury compensation, compensation for unfair dismissal, Which we will try to explain below:

Subsection One: End-of-service gratuity differentiation from the retirement pension

The Retirement and Social Security Law defines the pension as (the full or partial retirement salary that the institution pays to the insured, or his successor after him upon the end of his service, disability or death in accordance with the rules of the law), through the definition it becomes clear that the end-of-service

gratuity is shared with the retirement That both of them are paid to the worker after the end of his service, and they also share as compensation in cash and not in kind, but the end-of-service gratuity differs from retirement in terms of continuity and permanence, As the end-of-service gratuity is paid to the worker in one payment and for one time only, while the retirement salary is a cash amount paid to the worker on a continuous periodic basis, usually on a monthly basis. The end-of-service gratuity differs from the retirement salary in terms of the reason for entitlement, as the reason for the end-of-service gratuity is the end of the worker's service due to one of the reasons stipulated by law, Whereas, the entitlement to the retirement pension is based on age, service, disability, sickness or death, and the end-of-service gratuity is not entitled to the worker's heirs while the heirs of the retiree can benefit from the retirement salary in the event of the retiree's death.

Subsection Two End-of-service gratuity for compensation for work injury reward

A work injury can be defined (as having an occupational disease or an organic malfunction as a result of an accident that occurred during work or because of it, and it is considered as an accident that occurs to the insured worker during his direct going to work or during his direct return from it.) (Retirement Law) and as we knew previously the end-of-service gratuity is the amount paid by the Corporation to the insured in the event that the conditions for his entitlement to the pension are not met, or in other cases provided by law (6). By legal definition we can say that the compensation to which the worker is entitled as a result of the work injury is a monetary amount paid by the organization to the injured worker, it has in common with end-of-service gratuity that both are a sum of money paid to the worker, while end-of-service gratuity differs from Work injury compensation in terms of its calculation mechanism and the legal rules regulating its entitlement, as the provisions of calculating end-of-service gratuity depend mainly on the number of years of service, cases of contract termination, whether or not the worker is covered by the warranty, while we find that compensation for work injuries is a compensation For harm suffered by the worker as a result of the work.

Subsection three End-of-service gratuity for compensation for unfair dismissal

Unfair dismissal is defined as the termination of the work contract at the unilateral will of the employer for legitimate or illegitimate reasons, where the end-of-service gratuity participates with compensation for the unfair dismissal that the case of unfair dismissal is one of the reasons for the worker's entitlement to the end-of-service gratuity (7) as the end-of -service gratuity with compensation for unfair dismissal that their entitlement is based on law, Whereas end-of-service gratuity differs from compensation for unfair dismissal in that the rules for calculating them differ from the other, where compensation for unfair dismissal is calculated at the discretion of the judiciary as a result of the worker's claim for compensation, while end-of-service gratuity is calculated on the basis of years of service and age of the worker In addition, compensation for unfair dismissal includes, in some cases, returning the worker to his work with compensation if it has a legal basis. (8).

Chapter Two

Cases of termination of the employment contract

The issue of the termination of the work relationship has raised a lot of controversy regarding what results from the termination of that relationship, and the question also arises about how the work relationship ends, and although the result is the same, the effects are completely different. The employer, and in other cases, it terminates for a reason beyond the control of the parties, in addition to its termination according to the natural situation when the work contract is for a fixed term, Therefore, we will try to show the cases of termination of the work contract, as we deal in the first section with cases of the termination of the work contract by the unilateral will of the parties to the contract or one of them, then we deal with the termination of the work contract due to the impossibility of final implementation in the second section, then the termination of the work contract for a fixed term in the third section.

The first section

the termination of the work contract by the unilateral will of the two parties to the work contract or one of them

The general provisions in contracts binding on both sides have allowed one of the parties to the contract to request the judiciary to rescind it when its reasons are realized after warning the second party. In this case, the court may consider the debtor for a specified period or refuse the annulment, provided that the

two parties may consider the contract rescinded on its own and without the need to resort to the judiciary when the obligations arising from the contract are not fulfilled after warning the other party (9), However, it is also permissible to agree not to give notice, but this situation may not be consistent with the nature of work relationships, so labor laws may deviate from the provisions of the general provisions in this regard, as they allow both the worker and the employer the right to terminate the contract unilaterally without the need to resort to Judicial and warning the second party, whenever certain conditions specified by law are achieved, bearing in mind that the achievement of this matter is not always linked to the failure of one of the contracting parties to implement his contractual obligations, but rather for other reasons specified by law (10) Therefore, the work contract can be terminated by agreement between the two parties to the work contract, and termination can occur at the unilateral will of the employer or the worker.

The second section

the termination of the work contract due to the complete impossibility of implementation

The impossibility of implementation is an essential condition for the termination of the employment contract. Impossibility is a fact that makes the implementation of the contractor's obligation impossible. (11) Therefore, the general provisions of civil law stipulate that the incident that leads to the impossibility of implementation is a force majeure, in which it is stipulated that the incident is unexpected (12) to be obtained and cannot be paid and is not due to an error on the part of the debtor. Force majeure has an effect on the termination of the work contract due to the impossibility of implementing the obligation. It is also noted that the source of force majeure that leads to the impossibility of implementing the obligation is not considered. This impossibility may be due to an act of nature such as floods, earthquakes and volcanoes, and as in the case of the death of the worker or his prolonged illness, as it may refer to the order of the competent authorities as if the administrative authority issued a decision prohibiting the practice of an activity A specific occupation (13) It may be related to social or political events such as wars and revolutions that could lead to the destruction of the facility. Therefore, the impossibility of implementation leads to the expiration of the obligation of both the working parties and the employer. Therefore, the work contract is terminated by itself and by virtue of the law without the need for any special action taken by one of the parties to decide this termination. Therefore, final impossibility is what leads to the termination of the work contract (14) From this, there are two cases of final impossibility, namely the case of complete impossibility on the part of the worker in addition to complete impossibility on the part of the employer.

The third section

the termination of the fixed-term employment contract

A fixed-term employment contract is shared with an indefinite-term employment contract in cases of termination, with the exception of the case of unilateral termination of both parties. In addition, the Labor Law forbids specifying a term for the contract in works of a continuous nature, while it permits in business of an occasional, temporary and seasonal nature. The principle is the nature of the work subject of the contract, if it is of a permanent or temporary nature. The matter does not depend on the will of the two parties, but rather depends on the will of the legislator, who aimed from this provision to protect the worker from the employer's control not to make his fate in his own hand whenever he wants to use or dispense with him. But in cases where there is a condition stipulating the timing of the work contract in works of a continuous nature, this condition is invalidated and the contract that is concluded becomes of unlimited duration. (15) The first paragraph of Article 915 of the Iraqi Civil Code in force stipulates that: (16) If the contract (work for a fixed term expires on its own by the expiry of its period). The first paragraph of Article 916 of the same law stipulates that: The contract for carrying out a specific work ends with the expiry of the work agreed upon. It is clear from the preceding texts that the fixed-term work contract ends with the expiry of its term or the end of the agreed-upon work, and that the end of the fixed-term work contract is automatically and by force of law without the need to take a formal procedure and without the need for direction Notification and the reason for this due to the lack of the element of surprise and for both parties to know the date of the end of the contract (17) Therefore, according to determining the termination of the fixed-term work contract at the end of its term or the work agreed upon, the two parties cannot unilaterally terminate the work contract before the expiry of its term, but the two parties may agree to terminate the fixed-term work contract before the expiry of its term. However, there are some cases in which the employer or the worker has the right to terminate the work contract before the expiry of its term, such as in the case of

termination of the contract, in the case of impossibility and the state of the economic conditions he is going through. As for the work contract concluded for the life of the employer or worker, we find that the Iraqi legislator referred to this case in (18) Employer Article 902/2 where it stipulates that: If the contract is for the life of the worker or the employer or for more than five years, the worker may terminate the contract after five years without compensation, provided that the employer waits for six months. It is clear from this text that the work contract The contract for the life of the worker or the employer ends with the lapse of five years, as the law gives the worker the right to terminate it without the employer after five years have passed without the worker being committed to any compensation, provided that he informs the employer of six months until another worker is found (19).

Chapter Three

The mechanism of calculating the end of service gratuity

The relevant labor laws determine end-of-service gratuity, whether they are labor laws or social security laws, in addition to stipulating the rules for calculating end-of-service gratuity depending on the years of service, as well as whether it is covered by retirement and social security, or whether it has reached of a certain age and was not guaranteed or insured, among these legislations are the current Iraqi Labor Law and Law No. 39 of 1971 on Retirement and Social Security for Workers, The relevant legislation in the Arab countries also dealt with regulating the rules for calculating end-of-service gratuity in a varying manner from one law to another, and also included the cases under which the worker is deprived of end-of-service gratuity, so we will show the rules for calculating end-of-service gratuity. in the first section, then we indicate the cases under which the end-of-service gratuity is entitled in the second section, and we assign the third section to cases of denial of entitlement to end-of-service gratuity.

First section

Rules for calculating the end of service gratuity

Article 45 of the current Labor Law stipulates that (a worker whose service has ended shall be entitled to an end-of-service gratuity in the amount of two weeks' wages for each year of service performed with the employer...), while Article (20) of the Workers' Retirement and Social Security Law stipulates that if the worker service ends, who was not granted a retirement salary because he did not meet the conditions of entitlement, or because he is entitled to a full retirement salary from a non-establishment, shall be granted a total cash compensation in one payment representing an end-of-service gratuity, and it shall be calculated on the basis of his average monthly wage multiplied by the number of months of his service, and divided by Twelve, and the fraction of a month is calculated as a whole month...).

By reviewing the two texts, we see a clear difference in the rules for calculating end-of-service gratuity, between the current labor law and the retirement and social security law for workers, while it is calculated according to the labor law on the basis of the amount of two weeks' wages for each year of service, we find that the retirement and social security law has Adopt the rule of the average salary or monthly wage for the worker multiplied by the number of months of service and divided by (12) twelve, As the Retirement and Social Security Law was more equitable to the worker whose service has ended than the current Labor Law, if we assume that the worker's service was (20) years, then he is entitled to a wage of (40) forty weeks, which is equivalent to the wage of (11) eleven months of his total service, Whereas if we calculated the end-of-service gratuity under the Retirement and Social Security Law, the result of the equation would be twenty (20) months' wages, Here it is necessary to specify the applicable law, is it under the current labor law or under the retirement and social security law for workers? The Iraqi legislator did not indicate that when settling the end-of-service gratuity, if we take the rule of the later law superseding the previous law, the end-of-service gratuity will be in accordance with the current labor law, while the retirement and social security law provides better benefits for the terminated worker i.e. It is the best law for the worker, which is a clear legislative defect that must be addressed.

Second section

Cases of entitlement to end of service gratuity

Upon the termination of the worker's relationship with the employer, regardless of the reason for the termination of his service, except for some cases stipulated by the relevant laws, he is entitled to an end of service gratuity. where most of the legal legislations agree on the same conditions under which the worker is entitled to end-of-service gratuity, among them the Iraqi labor and social security legislations. Labor Law

No. 151 of 1970 stipulated a set of conditions for the worker to be entitled end-of-service gratuity when one of them is fulfilled. Which:

First, if the employer terminates the worker's services for any reason.

Secondly, if the service of the worker or user is terminated for any reason.

Third, upon the expiry of the period agreed upon between the worker or employee and the employer.

Fourth, if the woman leaves her service because of marriage.

Fifth: If the worker or employee reaches sixty years of age and is not covered by social security (21). While the previous Labor Law No. 71 of 1987 did not provide for end-of-service gratuity, the current Labor Law has included a statement of end-of-service gratuity upon termination of an employment contract (22). As for the current Retirement and Social Security Law, it mentioned several conditions under which the worker is entitled to end-of-service gratuity:

First, if the man has reached the age of sixty, or the working woman has reached the age of fifty-five.

Secondly, if the insured worker resigns from her job because of her marriage or status.

Third, if the worker is permanently outside the scope of the Labor Law.

Fourth, if he intends to leave the country permanently and the Minister agrees to his travel (23).

Third section

Deprivation of end-of-service gratuity

The current labor law stipulates cases of end-of-service gratuity for an employee, which are:

First, if the worker is sentenced by a final court ruling to imprisonment for more than one year, but if the sentence is less than one year, he shall be returned to his work, without being entitled to the wages of the period he spent in detention or imprisonment

Secondly, when the worker commits a behavior in violation of his duties under the work contract

Third, if the worker impersonates a false identity, or submits forged documents.

The results

Based on the foregoing, the research reached a set of results, which are listed below:

First: The insured worker is entitled to end-of-service gratuity in accordance with the law, regardless of the cases of termination of the work contract.

Second: The end-of-service gratuity is paid in the form of a cash sum to which the worker is entitled in the event of the end of his service if he is not covered by social security, in addition to the absence of conditions for his entitlement to the retirement salary or in other cases stipulated by law

Third: The end-of-service gratuity calculation mechanism in the Retirement and Social Security Law No. 39 of 1971 in force differs from the calculation mechanism in Labor Law No. 37 of 2015.

Fourth: The cases of calculating end-of-service gratuity in the Retirement and Social Security Law No. 39 of 1971 in force differ from the calculating mechanism in Labor Law No. 37 of 2015.

Fifth: The Iraqi Retirement and Social Security Law specified cases of depriving the worker of end-of-service gratuity, as they were limited to a group of cases, unlike the Arab legislation that expanded in this aspect.

Based on the foregoing results, the research reached a set of **recommendations**, which are listed below:

First: The need to provide the necessary financial allocations with the speedy payment of end-of-service gratuity to workers who are not entitled to the pension, because government departments complain about the lack of financial allocations that must be paid to this important category on which the country relied so much to build it.

Second: The need to work on resolving the discrepancy in calculating the end-of-service gratuity between Labor Law No. 37 of 2015 and Retirement and Social Security Law No. 39 of 1971 with the possibility of adopting the law that is best for the worker, which requires legislative intervention.

Third: The necessity of unifying end-of-service gratuity cases among Iraqi legislation to ensure receipt of funds by those who are entitled to it while ensuring that no element of this important category is unfair.

Fourth: Working on setting clearer criteria while studying the cases that deserve deprivation of this reward because the Iraqi legislation was brief with regard to this particular issue, in contrast to other Arab legislation that was more detailed, which ensured that the amounts reached the actual beneficiaries.

References

1. Article 1 of the Workers' Retirement and Social Security Law No. 39 of 1987.
2. Article (1 / fourteen) of the Unified Pension Law No. 9 of 2014.
3. Dr. Hassan Muhammad Hind, Explanation of the Provisions of the Labor Law, Part One, House of Legal Books, Cairo, 2007, p. 29
4. Dr. Muhammad Labib Shanab, Explanation of the Provisions of the Labor Law, First Edition, Al-Wafa Legal Library, Alexandria, 2010, p. 616.
5. Dr. Muhammad Labib Shanab, previous source, pg. 616
6. Article 1 of the Workers' Retirement and Social Security Law No. 39 of 1971.
7. Lawyer Nour Farhat Naim, Unfair dismissal in the Jordanian Labor Law, research published on the website. 2016/12/17 Last visit date WWW.Arablaw.com
8. Dr. Muhammad Labib Shanab, Explanation of the Provisions of the Labor Law, the Labor Law, first edition at Al-Wafa Press, Alexandria, 2010, p. 518.
9. (See Article (77/a) and Article (178) of the Iraqi Civil Code No. 40 of 1951.
10. Dr. Muhammad Ali Al-Taei. Labor Law, Dar Al Mahja Al Bayda, Beirut, 2008, p. 247.
11. Dr. Saba Numan Al-Waisi, Suspension of the Employment Contract and its Applications in Iraqi Law, MA Thesis/College of Law, University of Baghdad, 1998. pp. 31-30
12. Dr.. Hisham Rifaat Hashem, Explanation of the Jordanian Labor Law, Amman, Al-Muhtaseb Library, 1973, pp. 264-265.
13. Article 425 of the Iraqi Civil Code in force stipulates that: The obligation lapses if the debtor proves that fulfilling it has become impossible for a foreign reason that he has no control over.
14. Dr.. Muhammad Ali Al-Tai, a previous source, p. 254.
15. Muhammad Abdul-Khaleq Omar, previous source, pg. 416
16. Dr.. Qadri Abdel-Fattah Al-Shahawi, a previous source, p. 259.
17. Dr.. Muhammad Abdul-Khaleq Omar, previous source, pg. 416
18. Labor Law No. 151 of 1970.
19. Dr.. Adnan Al-Abed, Dr. Youssef Elias, Social Security Law, previous source, pp. 178-179.
20. Labor Law No. 37 of 2015, Articles 43, 44, 45.
21. UAE Labor Law No. 8 of 1980.
22. Labor and Social Retirement Law No. 39 of 1971.
23. Labor Law No. 37 of 2015, Articles 34 and 45.

The Golden Ratio in The Quran

M.M. Aripov, candidate of technical sciences
Associate Professor of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute
M.A. Mardankulova, master of the Kokand State Institute of Architecture
U.M. Oripova, bachelor of Tashkent State University of Law

Золотое Сечение В Коране

М.М.Арипов, кандидат технических наук
доцент Кокандского ГПИ
М.А.Марданкулова, магистр Кокандского ГПИ
У.М.Орипова, бакалавр Ташкентского ГЮУ

Annotation: The article on Abjad analyzes the full text of the Quran. It has been shown that the alteration of the text of the Quran by people is protected by Allah and that His main parameters depend on the divine golden ratio.

Key words: Abjad numbers, golden ratio, mathematical miracle, Quran.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada Qur'onning to'liq matni abjad sonlari orqali analiz qilingan. Qur'on matnini insonlar tomonidan o'zgartirish Alloh tomonidan himoya qilinganligi va Uni asosiy parametrlari ilohiy oltin nisbatga bog'liqligi ko'rsatib berilgan.

Аннотация: В статье по абджаду анализируется полный текст Корана. Было показано, что изменение текста Корана людьми, защищено Аллахом и что Его основные параметры зависят от божественного золотого сечения.

Kalit so'zlar: Abjad raqamlari, oltin nisbat, matematik mo'jiza, Qur'on.

Ключевые слова: числа Абджад, золотое сечение, математическое чудо, Коран.

На протяжении всей истории многие ученые пытались предоставить доказательства, подтверждающие божественное происхождение Корана. Фактически, многие видные ученые сочли Коран в целом лучше, чем все популярные литературные произведения. Действительно, мощный стиль Корана, по-видимому, несовместим с какими-либо существующими хорошо известными литературными произведениями [1].

Ученые приложили много усилий для поиска истин и фактов Корана, особенно тех, которые связаны с доктриной чудесности Корана, чтобы обосновать и доказать ее достоверность и полное участие Аллаха в раскрытии Корана [2-3]. В результате появились недавние исследовательские попытки закрепить божественное авторство Корана с использованием различных концепций и методологий. Введение теории Рашада Халифы о 19 в 1974 году, тогда как число 19 - это код, на котором математически структурирован Благородный Коран [2,4] и, по его словам, число 19 численно действует как общий знаменатель.

В самом деле, в Коране было много интересных схем и связей такого рода, которые не могли возникнуть случайно. Подобно подходу Халифы, Абдул Даем Аль-Кахил доказал важность числа 7 во многих случаях в Коране [5]. В аналогичном качестве Джаррар [6] также задокументировал

множество интересных математических закономерностей в Коране, используя систему чисел Абджад.

Всемогущий Аллах имеет встроенные механизмы защиты, основанные на математических алгоритмических функциях. Таким образом, раскрытие любого из этих алгоритмов поможет раскрыть многие секреты Корана, особенно те, которые связаны с основными параметрами Корана, а также с тем, как дизайн Корана связан с золотым сечением. Эта теория была разработана на основе популярной системы счисления Абджад [12,13]. Система счисления Абджад была очень популярна задолго до ислама, в которой 28 арабским алфавитом присвоены числовые значения (см. Таблицу 1).

Фактически, этот метод расчета широко использовался задолго до откровения Корана, и даже до развития римских или арабских систем счисления, которые мы знаем сегодня. Эта система счисления использовалась для предсказания будущего, и этот тип систем счисления был обычным явлением в анналах истории. Однако нет никаких свидетельств, подтверждающих происхождение системы счисления Абджад. Исторически происхождение этой числовой системы неизвестно и до сих пор остается загадкой, даже многие заявляли, что эта система имеет божественное происхождение [8]. Однако о некоторых интересных математических закономерностях в Коране сообщил Джаррар [7], который широко использовал систему счисления Абджад.

Коран был открыт в течение 23 лет и был написан на арабском языке с использованием основных 28 алфавитов арабского языка (см. Образец первого рисунка Корана: рис. 1). В работе [12] использовано текстовое содержание следующих трех божественных компонентов: (1) Коран, который состоит из 6236 аятов и 114 сур, (2) 112 нунумерованных басмал и (3) названия 114 сур. Комитет экспертов из различных арабских стран во главе с Абдул Даем Аль-Кахил Сирии работал в течение почти семи лет, чтобы разработать цифровую копию Корана и сборки программного обеспечения для обеспечения поиска объектов в Коране. Они установили стандарты для вычисления статистики Корана (буквы и слова), которые полностью основаны на первом рисунке Корана: эти стандарты чрезвычайно важны для установления правильных правил и руководящих принципов для подсчета букв и слов [7]. Таким образом, чтобы гарантировать полное соответствие с первым рисунком Корана, буква засчитывается только в том случае, если она написана физически [7]. Это важное требование ранее не учитывалось в процессе подсчета писем во многих исследованиях, поэтому методы подсчета были непоследовательными. Первой сложной задачей, стоящей перед упомянутым выше комитетом, было то, как написать Коран в компьютеризированном формате, чтобы функции, предоставляемые

Рис.1. Образец первого рисунка Корана

могли быть легко применены к оцифрованному формату Корана. Для достижения этой цели технический комитет во главе с Аль-Кахилом принял те же правила, которые использовались при написании первого текста Корана. Следующим шагом, после преобразования коранического текста в цифровой формат, была проверка текста на полное соответствие усманскому тексту Корана. Также была проведена проверка совместимости слово за словом и буква за буквой с оцифрованным

документом Корана, выпущенным Комплексом печати Корана короля Фахда в Саудовской Аравии (2017 г.).

Программное обеспечение Аль-Кахила [8] выдало результаты, показанные на Таблице 2. Текстуально весь Коран представляет собой сумму всех трех божественных компонентов (см. Таблицу 3):

В работе [12] вычислена абджадская ценность Корана на основе первого рисунка Корана. Первым шагом исследования является вычисление общей ценности Абджада (V) Корана, которая равна сумме значений Абджад трех божественных компонентов Корана, как уже упоминалось. Во-первых, из Таблицы 3 очевидно, что вычисленное значение Абджада Корана (114 глав, 6236 стихов, 86967 слов и 322604 буквы) равно 23378278. Во-вторых, общее значение Абджада для 19 букв, составляющих Бисмиллах, составляет 786, таким образом, общая стоимость Абджада 112 нумерованных Бисмиллах составляет ($= 112 \times 786$) 88032 (Таблица 3). В-третьих, общее значение абджада 652 букв в именах 114 глав составляет 40234 (таблица 2). Наконец, общая стоимость Абджада (V) Священного Корана представляет собой сумму трех компонентов ($23378278 + 88032 + 40234$), что равно 23506544 (Таблица 3) [12].

Важность общей стоимости абджада (23506544), заключается в том, что это число включает в себя общую ценность абджада всего Корана. Очевидно, общая ценность Абджада всего Корана действует как защитный механизм, чтобы защитить текст Корана от вмешательства и дополнения со стороны человека.

В работе [12] вычисляется общая сумма номеров каждого отдельного аята (см. Таблицу 2). Например, в суре 1 - 7 аятов, поэтому ее сумма составляет $1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 = 28$. а в суре 2 - 286 аятов, поэтому его сумма составляет $1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + 286 = 41041$, и это проходит через остальную часть Корана, давая окончательную сумму 333667 (Таблица 2): уникальное простое число само по себе. Очевидно, совокупная сумма номеров аятов Корана (333667) играет центральную роль в защите организационной структуры Корана от искажения его физического устройства.

Таким образом, это золотое число (333667) действует как защитный механизм для защиты структурного устройства Корана. Действительно, это простое число обладает уникальными математическими свойствами, которые издавна восхищали математиков. Следовательно, выбор совокупной суммы номеров аятов равной 333667 должен быть действием сверхъестественного разума. Это серьезное подтверждение того, что сверхъестественный Создатель должен был участвовать в разработке Корана.

Таблица 1. Абджадские значения арабского алфавита

ا	ب	ج	د	ه	و	ز	ح	ط	ي	ك	ل	م	ن
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	20	30	40	50
س	ع	ف	ص	ق	ر	ش	ت	ث	خ	ذ	ض	ظ	غ
60	70	80	90	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800	900	1000

Таблица 2. Общее количество аятов, общая сумма номеров аятов, общее количество букв сур

Номера сур	Название суры	Количество аятов суры	Сумма номеров ята	Кол. букв в наз. суры	Значение абджада названия суры
1	الفاتحة	7	28	7	525
2	البقره	286	41041	6	338
3	ال عمران	200	20100	7	392
....					...
113	الفن	5	15	5	241
114	الناس	6	21	5	142
	Сумма	6236	333667	652	40234

Таблица 3. Общее количество букв, слов и значение абджада всего Корана:
три божественных компонента

Компоненты	Количество букв	Количество слов	Значение абджада
Каран (6236 аятов)	322604	86967	23378278
112 не номерованных Басмала	2128 (19×112)	448 (4×112)	88032 (786×112)
Назвние суры	652	115	40234
Сумма	325384	87530	23506544

Примечание: Каждая Басмала состоит из 4 слов и 19 букв с общим значением абджада 786.

Второе числовое значение должен иметь математические свойства, управляющие организационной структурой Корана. Определенно, структурный дизайн Корана в основном связан с сурами и аятами, и тем, как аяты распределяются по разным главам, каждая глава имеет определенное количество аятов, от 3 до 286. Распределение аятов по сурам исторически подтверждено как божественное установление [8]. Распределение сур/аятов является важным критерием для определения того, как Коран структурирован по сурам. Единственное числовое значение, которое потенциально может быть кандидатом на роль сохранения структуры - это совокупная сумма номеров аятов (333667) (Таблица 2). Определенно, это числовое значение управляет организационной структурой Корана, посредством чего оно не позволяет перемещать каких-либо аятов из суры в другую, а также добавлять или удалять аятов. Таким образом, это важное число действует как механизм защиты от любой попытки вмешательства в физическую структуру Корана.

Удивительно, у числа (333667) есть много уникальных атрибутов и характеристик, которые делают его одним из самых важных, если не самым важным шестизначным простым числом. Сумма его цифр (3 + 3 + 3 + 6 + 6 + 7) равна 28 (что является общим количеством арабских алфавитов). Кроме того, если мы умножим каждую цифру этого простого числа на следующую цифру и сложим результаты (3 x 3) + (3 x 3) + (3 x 6) + (6 x 6) + (6 x 7), получится 114, что равно общему числу сур Корана. Кроме того, это 6-значное простое число обладает множеством интересных математических свойств, которые отличают его от всех 6-значных простых чисел. Во-первых, простой фактор 333667 - это наибольший простой фактор палиндрома 12345678987654321. Во-вторых, наибольший простой фактор 9-значного повторения цифр равен 333667. В-третьих, когда любое 3-значное число умножается на 333667 и 3, результатом всегда будет одно и то же 3-значное число повторяется 3 раза. Например, $111 \times 333667 \times 3 = 111111111$. Поистине, никогда не может быть простым совпадением, что сумма чисел аятов Корана равна 333667, потому что это уникальное шестизначное простое число вряд ли будет использовано в разработке Корана через человеческое участие в то время, когда Коран был ниспослан 1400 лет назад. Определенно, сегодняшних систем нумерации не существовало во время откровения Корана, и очевидно, что ни один человек в то время не мог оценить уникальные и интересные математические свойства этого простого числа (333667). Следовательно, это должна быть божественная сила, сверхъестественно оформленная в Коране таким образом, чтобы общая сумма номеров аятов Корана равнялась 333667.

Золотое сечение (ϕ) математически просто и обычно приближается к числу 1,618. Золотому сечению приписывают множество интересных математических свойств, которые делают его уникальным среди всех чисел [9]. Золотое сечение повсеместно проявилось при проектировании и строительстве многих живых и неживых объектов в природе. Действительно, золотое сечение обладает математическими свойствами и характеристиками, которым, кажется, следуют многочисленные природные объекты и явления. Многие ученые называют золотое сечение отпечатком пальца Аллаха, который проявляется повсюду в природе [10]. В природе любой дизайн продукта, основанный на золотом сечении, кажется естественным образом связан с Создателем. Категорически это божественное соотношение является естественным математическим принципом.

Многие считают, что золотое сечение является фундаментальной характеристикой Вселенной [9,10]. Благодаря уникальным математическим свойствам золотого сечения все священные писания широко подвергались числовому анализу разной степени, чтобы так или иначе связать их с золотым сечением, чтобы доказать их божественность, достоверность и божественное авторство.

Одно из основных намерений исследования [12] - продемонстрировать, существует ли какая-либо числовая связь между Кораном и золотым сечением. Действительно, без сомнения доказано, что многие живые и неживые объекты подчиняются математическим правилам и свойствам золотого сечения. Определенно, если Коран был создан Всемогущим Аллахом, наиболее вероятно, что существует связь между Кораном и золотым сечением.

Кроме того, известно, что Благородный Коран имеет различные важные цифры, которые составляют его структуру и дизайн. Наиболее заметным среди мусульман является общее количество сур, при этом Коран состоит из 114 сур разной длины, от 3 до 286 аятов, и каждый аят имеет длину от двух букв до полной страницы. Другими словами, текст Корана физически состоит из 114 сур и был исполнен посредством полного божественного участия согласно многочисленным ссылкам. Таким образом, возникает важный вопрос: существует ли количественная связь между D, и общим количеством глав (114)? Мы пишем

$$\varphi = 114 \times \frac{D}{V} = 114 \times \frac{333667}{23506544} = 1,618189301$$

где V – суммарное значение абджада Корана, D – сумма номеров аята.

Примечательно то, что соотношение общего количества глав Корана (114), которое представляет собой физический дизайн Корана, D и V, которая представляет собой математический дизайн Корана, чрезвычайно близко согласуется с идеальным золотым сечением (1,6180339887). Высокоточная оценка золотого сечения в Коране и других Священных Книгах никогда ранее не была достигнута, хотя многие различные исследования различных методологий, подходов и техник были применены ко всем монотеистическим писаниям. Определенно, этот замечательный результат является чрезвычайно убедительным доказательством, которое обеспечивает явную поддержку божественного авторства Корана.

Несомненно, этот важный результат всесторонне доказывает, что Коран структурирован таким образом, что он следует схеме золотого сечения и, следовательно, согласно сверхчеловеческому разумному замыслу. Наличие золотого сечения в дизайне и структуре Корана подразумевает, что для этой Священной Книги должен быть Создатель [10]. В самом деле, без всяких разумных сомнений, это математическое явление не может произойти по чистой случайности или совпадению, потому что вероятность наличия этого великого математического явления в конструкции Корана практически бесконечно мала.

Одна из наиболее выдающихся особенностей этой теории заключается в том, что она полностью основана на тексте, переданном Пророку Мухаммеду и нарисованному с использованием основных 28 алфавитов арабского языка, который состоит из 6236 аятов и физически организован в 114 глав (рукопись Османа). Буква засчитывается, если она написана физически, и это точно соответствует первому рисунку Корана. Это числовое значение можно использовать для защиты Корана от любых искажений и изменений.

Список литературы

1. Abdul-Raof. Qur'an Translation: Discourse, Texture and Exegesis, Curzon Press.2000.
2. Khalifa, R. MIRACLE OF THE QURAN: Significance of the Mysterious Alphabets, Islamic Productions, St. Louis, Missouri.1973.
3. Deedat, Ahmed. Al-Quran, The Miracle of Miracles. Durban: Islamic Propagation Centre, 1991.
4. Khalifa, R. The Computer Speaks: God's Message to the World. Renaissance Productions International.1981

5. Al-Kaheel, A. *Ishraqat al-Raqam Sab`a fial-Qur'an al-Karim*. Dubai: Dubai International Holy Quran.2006.
6. Jarrar, B. *Numeric Miracles of the Holy Qur'an Chosen Examples*. Al-Bireh: Noon Center for Qur'anic Studies & Research.2001
7. Al-Suyuti. *Alal al-Deen Al-Suyuti, Al-Itqan fi Ulum Al-Quran*, vol. 1, Cairo, n.d., p. 147. 1948.
8. Haleem, M. A. *Understanding the Qur'an : themes and style*. I.B. Tauris. p. 82. 2005.
9. Kak S. *The golden mean and the physics of aesthetics*. In *Ancient Indian leaps into mathematics* (pp. 111-119). Birkhäuser Boston. 2009.
10. Livio, M. *The golden ratio: The story of phi, the world's most astonishing*
11. *number*. Broadway Books. 2008.
12. Aboul-Enein, B. H. *Health-promoting verses as mentioned in the Holy Quran*.
13. *Journal of religion and health*, 55(3), 821-829. 2016.
14. Khaled M.S. *A mathematical Phenomenon in the Quran of Earth-Shattering*
15. *Proportions: A Quranic Theory Based on Gematria Determining Quran*
16. *Primary Statistics (words, verses, chapters) and Revealing its Fascinating*
17. *Connection with the Golden Ratio*.
18. M.M.Aripov, R.N.Normatov, I.M.Siddikov, U.Oripova. *Fundamentals of creating the algebra science and algorithms*. *Solid State Technology*. 63(5), 6094-6102, 2020.
19. Арипов М.М., Орипова У.М. *Математические феномены Корана. Современная наука. XXI век: научный, культурный, ИТ контекст. Сборник статей I Международной научно-практической конференции*. с.29-36, Омск, 2021.

Old and new challenges and threats in Algerian political life

Rasulov Otabek Abdulazizovich,

Lecturer at the Department of International Relations and
Social Sciences of the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan

Abstract. This article analyzes changes, which occur in Algerian political life, as well as threats of terrorists and interests of the outside forces toward Algeria. Religious extremists of the previous age led to Civil war in this region. However, successful operations of Algeria against terrorist lead to cooperation with neighboring countries and fight against terrorists.

Key words: Overseas Security Advisory Council (OSAC), Jund al-Khilafah in Algeria (JAK-A), ISIS-Algeria, improvised explosive devices (IEDs), Khenchela, Chlef, Ain Djelfa, Tissemsilt and Medea, Adrar, Tamanrasset, political spring, Dark Decade.

The relatively recent change in leadership and the prolonged economic stagnation could lead to continued stability in Algeria, with serious consequences for the security of the country and the region as a whole, as well as for the interests of outside forces, particularly the US, EU, Russia and China.

In recent years, Due to increasing activities of extremist and terrorist organizations in North Africa and the Middle, Algeria's role as a regional base in the fight against terrorism has increased significantly.

According to annual report of the Overseas Security Advisory Council (OSAC) in 2020. Terrorist groups remain active in the Sahara region. AQIM, AQIM-allied groups, and ISIS elements, including the Algerian affiliate locally known as Jund al-Khilafah in Algeria (JAK-A, now calling itself ISIS-Algeria), are present. These groups aspire to attack Algerian security services, local government targets, and Western interests. Almost all reported terrorist attacks in 2018 targeted Algerian security forces and involved improvised explosive devices (IEDs) or ambush tactics as suspects actively fled through rural mountainous regions.¹

Experts say the number of terrorist groups in Algeria has decreased, however terrorist networks continue recruiting militants in neighboring countries, including Libya and Mali. Algerian terrorist groups sought out new members in Algerian schools and mosques in the early 2000s, particularly targeting young unemployed. Regular raids by Algerian security forces show that the problem of terrorism remains in the country, and threat of it will increase if disagreements among Algerian society and elite of the government escalate.

The Algerian government is cracking down on terrorist activities with the security apparatus. In 2018, the national army destroyed nearly a dozen terrorists, during a series of cleanups. In January 2018, a major operation took place in the province of Khenchela, where security forces killed a group of terrorists trying to unite the remaining groups in Algeria, including prominent leaders of the Tunisian AQIM. Police have also arrested more than 50 terrorists across the country. Furthermore, 129 terrorists have surrendered, who were active in the south of the country.

The Algerian army on Tuesday eliminated the leader of the terrorists in the valley of Ain Djelfa, located southwest of the capital city of Algiers. In 1997, he joined terrorist groups, was the leader of terrorists operating in Chlef, Ain Djelfa, Tissemsilt and Medea.² Algeria has also reportedly deployed tens of thousands of troops along its borders with Mali and Libya to prevent terrorist attacks and arms transfers. Despite positive results in uncovering terrorist plots, reconnaissance warns Algeria that direct cross-border threats remain.

¹ Algeria 2020 Crime & Safety Report // U.S. Department of State. Overseas Security Advisory Council. - 6/9/2020 . - <https://www.osac.gov/Content/Report/aceef5ea-f045-453b-8fc9-18e3d2222273>.

² Новости «Синьхуа». - RUSSIAN.NEWS.CN. - 13 мая 2020 г. - http://russian.news.cn/2020-05/13/c_139053240.htm.

On September 17, 2020, in the annual report of US intelligence on global threats to Congress Christopher Miller, Director of the US National Counterterrorism Center said, "ISIS is able to rebuild itself by continuing to pursue an aggressive global strategy toward Africa. At present, the group has 20 interconnected groups around the world, especially on the Black Continent, which frequently attacks local law enforcement agencies and expands its territory".³ Outside the mountainous border with Algeria, ISIS terrorists have not given up trying to expand the battlefield to an important area for Tunisia. ISIS terrorists are not giving up their efforts to expand the battlefield beyond the mountainous border with Algeria to an important zone for Tunisia, expanding the scope of operations to countries with a low terrorist threat in the African tropics, particularly Cote d'Ivoire and Mozambique.

In Algeria, the number of seizures of firearms, explosives, grenade launchers has increased, and security forces are destroying terrorist hideouts in various parts of the country, especially in the border areas of the southern desert of Adrar and Tamanrasset. More recently, in December, the government intercepted deep-air heavy artillery, including air-to-surface missiles, sent to local terrorist groups through regional arms smuggling networks. According to the report fighting on the border led to a reduction in the main areas of human trafficking, and in the summer of 2018, additional guard towers, patrols and trenches were set up. This is in line with the record number of terrorists who surrendered in 2018, the increase in the number of weapons confiscated, and the number of terrorist hideouts.

With the most unfortunate clash of domestic and foreign political and economic factors, it is undeniable that the situation in the country in the second decade of the 2000s could once again spiral out of control. Religious extremism and tribal opposition still remain a problem for Algeria's internal stability, as well as the precarious situation on its borders with Libya, Morocco, Western Sahara and Mali. Wide areas across the country and borders that are difficult to manage by the DPRK pose a potential threat to stability within the country.

In general, the situation in North Africa in the fight against the threat of terrorism remains a threat to the security of all countries in the region. Although terrorist groups in Africa are known to have mostly local targets, they are colluding with their brethren outside the continent, which has created local al-Qaeda cells and trying to build "the Islamic State". On the African continent, especially in the Sahel region, it has lost ground in Iraq and Syria. The number of foreign terrorists is increasing on the African Continent on the border of large-capacity countries. They exploit local dissatisfaction, poverty, lack of public services and security, engage in cross-border criminal activity and pose a serious threat to national and regional security. At the same time, with the help of foreign troops, the ongoing war in Libya is intensifying terrorist activity in the region, adversely affecting the situation in North Africa.

Social agitation in the nation can occupy the administration of the Democratic Republic of Algeria from the battle against psychological warfare, and surprisingly open up space for the exercises of different radical associations and aggressor associations in Algeria. This will permit criminal fanatic and psychological militant gatherings in the district to move all closer and possibly to adjoining Europe.

Such a development of the situation would be associated with additional risks and problems. In particular, the growing threat of instability and terrorism in Algeria may increase the interest of outside forces, in particular the United States and the European Union, in interfering in the country's affairs. American researcher J. As Porter pointed out: "Instability in Algeria would affect the United States' regional partners, including Nigeria and countries in southern Europe, which are concerned about spillover from potential terrorist activity in Algeria's south and increased migration to Europe from its north. Although the United States has limited influence on events in Algeria, Washington can take worthwhile steps to manage the risk

³ Hearing before the U.S. House of Representatives Committee on Homeland Security. // Published in the National Counterterrorism center (NCTC) Newsroom. Office of the Director of National Intelligence. - Thursday, 17 September 2020. 16:58. - <https://www.dni.gov/index.php>.

of growing political instability, including precautionary measures to safeguard its interests should the worst happen.”⁴

Most analysts in the region and in the West say that despite long-standing problems such as failed political systems and ineffective economic policies, the Algerian leadership and ordinary people, who have suffered from the effects of the civil war, attach great importance to domestic political stability. Due to this factor, Algeria has managed to maintain its current political "status quo" for many years.

However, the country is vulnerable to unpredictable threats such as unrest and violence during the so-called "political spring" of 1988. At the time, Algeria's economy was in a crisis due to extremely low oil prices, and civil society questioned the legitimacy of the government.

Russian scientist R.G. Landa: “The religious fanaticism of the second half of the 1980s, as well as ethnic identity, were partly reflected in the growing popular discontent with the deteriorating economic situation, the polarization of incomes, and the widening gap between the upper and lower classes. Encouragement from private sector administrators has yielded positive results, as well as at sea.” The unrest, which began in the country in October 1988,⁵ led to political and economic liberalization, resulting in the civil war of the 1990s, which is known as Algeria's "Dark Decade."

⁴ Porter G. D. Political Instability in Algeria. // Contingency Planning Memorandum No. - Center for Preventive Action. Council on Foreign Relations. - Washington, 35 March 07, 2019. - <https://www.cfr.org/report/political-instability-algeria>.

⁵ Ланда Р.Г. История Алжира. XX век. – Институт востоковедения Российской Академии наук. – М., 1996 г. – 309 с. - С. 201.

Professional And Personal Characteristics of Leadership Individually Leadership

Elmurodov Ulug'bek Yusup og'li

Assistant of the Department of General Psychology,
Samarkand State University
elmurodulugbek32@gmail.com

Annotation. The article analyzes the work done in the leadership and management system, theoretical and practical aspects of leadership psychology in the new era of management psychology.

Key words. Management, leadership, interpersonal relations, subject leader, professional competence, informational roles

Systematization and improvement of the management process in all areas of the world has always been a priority. Management activities are carried out by a formally appointed manager, and the effectiveness of the enterprise or institution depends in many respects on the manager's management style, knowledge, skills, and leadership skills, professional and personal qualities. In particular, leadership skills are formed by a manager who creates a positive social environment with employees and leads the team to success the emergence of the concept of governance is a process that takes place in close connection with the development of society. The content and essence of management science is related to the management of naming people or team work activities together. As the team grows, management tasks become more complex. The complexity of the management process necessitates the use of management science. The management system is an open complex system, which consists of two parts: the object and the subject.

The object and subject of the study of management psychology is a separate person. Their psychological states, some of the processes and tasks in them are said to be the object of management.

When the subject of management is studied, it usually refers to the person or group of people in charge. An object is a controlled system and a subject is a controller. Management science is divided into the following types.

1. Management theory
2. Management analysis
3. Knowledge of management methods
4. Knowledge of management
5. Knowledge of management psychology

The organizational and psychological department of management science is a central part of the management system and defines team management; production. A leader in a civilized society should be distinguished from others by his spirituality, perfection, devotion, faith, patriotism, and special abilities. Only through a thorough mastery of the basics of management psychology, it is possible to form in each person a high sense of humor, a positive attitude to work, social activism, a sense of comfort.

In our country, great attention is paid to reforming the governing bodies, training young people in professions that are in high demand in the labor market, raising the prestige of scientific activity, training modern leaders and conducting research in this area. [1]

So far, our scientists have conducted a lot of research on the study and development of management competencies in management. The qualities that determine the professional competence of a leader are highlighted, and the correction of the tendency to Machiavellianism, which negatively affects professional competence, is studied in practice. However, in the world and in our country, no attention has been paid to the study of leadership formation as ability. [2] Truss said that while ambition and career advancement are key to the success of management, they are not the only conditions. [3] Therefore, the results of the activities of many modern leaders can be seen as interesting facts of their rise in the career ladder. The role of interpersonal relationships encompasses the manager's relationship with employees.

There are roles of leader, leader and connecting link in this field. A leader must play a leading role with official authority and symbolic status as a representative of his or her organization. As a leader, the manager must combine the needs of the organization and the individual employees who work with and manage it. The third interpersonal role - the connecting link - covers the area of horizontal relationships.

Information roles. The leader must constantly work with the data to perform the three appropriate aggregator, distributor, and representative roles.

The decision-making role includes the roles of initiator, problem solver, resource allocator, and negotiator. A culture of dominance - a leader in an organization where this type of culture is predominant, his personal qualities and abilities play a key role. The resources at the disposal of the leader are used as a source of power. Organizations with such a culture have a strictly hierarchical structure. Recruitment and promotion to the top of the career ladder is often done on the basis of personal loyalty. This type of culture allows the organization to respond quickly to changes in the situation, make quick decisions, and organize their implementation; [4]

Role culture is characterized by a strict functional division of roles and specialization of areas. This type of organization operates on a system of rules, processes, and standards, and adherence to it guarantees its effectiveness. The main source of management is not personal qualities, but a position held in a hierarchical structure. Such an organization is capable of operating successfully in a stable environment;

Task culture - this type of culture is primarily aimed at solving problems, implementing projects. The effectiveness of organizations with such a culture depends largely on the high professionalism of the staff and the effectiveness of the cooperative group. Those who are experts in the leading field of activity and have maximum knowledge have great power in such organizations. Situational requirements in this cultural activity are effective when they play a central role in the activities of the organization.

A culture of personality - an organization with this type of culture unites people to achieve their goals, not to solve any problems.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the psychology of management is recognized as a new, modern and a lot of research in the field of psychology. By incorporating the theoretical and practical aspects of management psychology into the life of society, various conflict situations that may occur between teams, between employees, will be prevented, and production will continue to grow, both quantitatively and qualitatively.

List Of Used References:

1. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан от 5 июля 2017 года № ПФ-5106 «О повышении эффективности государственной молодежной политики и поддержке деятельности Союза молодежи Узбекистана».
2. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан № ПФ-4947 от 7 февраля 2017 года «О стратегии дальнейшего развития Республики Узбекистан».
3. Sh.N. Zaynuddinov. I.U.Murakaev. Fundamentals of management. Tashkent Finance 2007
4. S.S.Kasimov., N.A.Muminov Leadership and management skills. Prepring T. 2001. 56 pages

The issues of spiritual growth, morality and ethics in society are in the works of our enlightened scholars

Retired **Major Akhmedov Murodjon Mahmudovich**,
teacher of special sciences, Tashkent Academic Lyceum No. 2 of the
Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Israilova Shakhnoza Tolkinovna,
head of the department of the Tashkent Academic Lyceum No. 2 of the
Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Announcement: It is aimed at ensuring the rule of law in New Uzbekistan and promoting human rights and legitimate interests.

Keywords: "Mahbulul-qulub" (beloved of hearts) "Your body is a horse, you are a rider."

It is no secret that the interests of the people are at the heart of the comprehensive reforms being carried out in our country.

In modern Uzbekistan, all government agencies and officials are focused on upholding the rule of law and serving human rights and legitimate interests. The role of law enforcement agencies in this activity, as in all areas, is invaluable. In a strong democratic state and a just civil society, special emphasis is placed on ensuring human rights, freedoms and interests. It is the protection of human interests, its position in society, which in turn affects the development of socio-economic, cultural and other spheres of society. The work done in recent years in this regard is commendable. In an interview with the editor-in-chief of the New Uzbekistan, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. At the same time, there are shortcomings and problems that are in the constant focus of the head of state. As one of them, it is not new that the study of the existing literary heritage is not enough to develop the legal consciousness and culture in the society, to ensure public security in the true sense of the word. This is primarily a flaw that undermines human rights and legitimate interests. I think that the prevention of such defects will give good results and results by studying the works of scholars who have lived in our country in history. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev has repeatedly called on young people and everyone to love the book, which leads to spiritual maturity. It is not in vain.

The fact that reading is initiated by the head of state is a clear proof that it has the highest goals. Every being needs a mineral in some sense for its normal functioning and survival. Unlike other living beings, it is absorbed by man through reading and knowing. A citizen who does not violate the rights of others is obedient to the law. Such skills are certainly derived from ancestral teachings. We have such a literary heritage in this regard that it is recognized, envied and constantly studied by the world. In this regard, it is worth noting one of the ideas of J. Rumi, "Your body is a horse, you are a rider. Let not the horseman leave the horse without a stable, but let him not fall into it. Horse sucking is not food for the rider. You did not lead the horse in your own way, the horse led you in its own way ... " What a clear and beautiful expression. Unfortunately, as a result of illiteracy, ignorance, lack of learning and laziness, there are "horsemen" in the society. It is for this reason that violations of the law are taking place, and this has an impact on public safety. It is no exaggeration to say that the activities of the libraries established in the local law enforcement agencies with new content are one of the steps towards raising the legal awareness and culture in the society, towards a spiritually rich and perfect humanity. Everyone who comes to the neighborhood law enforcement center will instinctively fall in love with the book when they see the books there. He strives to read the books recommended to him, enriches his inner world and avoids unnecessary activities. That is why the place of immortal and invaluable literary heritage is so important. The thoughts expressed by the scholars, their works lead people to goodness. In this regard, in the work of our ancestor A.Navoi "Mahbulul-qulub" (beloved of the heart), he spoke about good deeds and bad qualities, and expressed his views on such qualities as contentment, patience, mercy, fidelity and modesty, and modesty and gentleness. Many of our scholars have described in detail the characteristics that people seem to lack in

the present time, and the ways to achieve them. The task of the present generation is to study them, use them wisely and pass them on to the next generation. Such actions, of course, ensure security in society and prevent crime. Life experiences show that it is committed by people who are indifferent to the development of the people and society, ignorant of science, morally and spiritually poor. At present, the task of everyone in our society is to focus on this category of people.

It is a partnership with neighborhoods that are yielding good results along the way. Now it is necessary to carry out this work on the part of every citizen, of course, every measure taken to prevent crime requires a planned, systematic approach. It is in this system that a special place is given to the works of great scholars and thinkers. Especially today's information threats, a lot of nonsensical information can not meet the requirements of our society. People are filling the information deficit with these harmful flaws. As a result, a gap is emerging in society and it is attracting many. The works of many of our scholars play an important role in filling this gap. Indeed, in times of change, people, times, good and evil, lust and envy, modesty, modesty, chastity and other virtues always have the same appearance and content. You just have to be more discriminating with the help you render toward other people. It is necessary to make effective use of the work of our scholars in all events and conversations with offenders and their predecessors.

To do this, those who interact with them need to read and know more. Our society faces many trials and tribulations. As the President said, "together we will overcome them." It is on this path that we need to understand and know ourselves more.

It is expedient to rely on our own "eastern" culture, rather than the "western" culture that is now entering our society. After all, not every innovation that comes from outside is always good. Although the West admits that it received its awakening from the East, what else can we get from them? Being steady and steady on this path will definitely pay off. After all, education can cure all ills. This is especially true of A. Avloni's work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality". The play contains clear ideas about education, intellect, knowledge, zeal, patriotism, justice, generosity and other good qualities. By knowing this, man will surely illuminate his way of life with the light of enlightenment. In turn, bad behaviors such as anger, enmity, selfishness, gossip, jealousy, slander, and insults were also commented on. These negative evils, especially now in our society, are unfortunately very common. There is no doubt that by knowing the ideas expressed in the work of A. Avloni, a person can find his place in society if he has good morals and is free from negative vices. This work needs to be studied and applied by all people in our society, especially those involved in human education. By knowing, using and avoiding the good and bad behaviors that occur in life, it is possible to objectively evaluate the actions of each person, compare them, and, if necessary, determine the necessary measures.

It is characteristic of the perfect man to seek knowledge from the "cradle to the grave", and the extent to which he knows the sciences constitutes the meaning of man's way of life.

Therefore, like all other spheres, it is important to use the works of our great scholars more widely in ensuring security, human rights and freedoms in society, and in preventing crime. There is no doubt that the more we study them, the more we adhere to them, the more we will be able to achieve the enlightened goal of our people only if we unite "together" in the pursuit of a single goal. This path requires a lot of attention, it is not without difficulties, and in the end it is a path that celebrates goodness. In an interview with the editor-in-chief of the above-mentioned newspaper, the President gave a clear definition of this, including "New Uzbekistan will become a prosperous and prosperous country with a strong potential, a worthy reputation in the world arena." I sincerely wish our people and every citizen good luck in this work, our country will be peaceful and the sky will be clear. After all, as our people and scholars say, "it is good to strive."

References

1. Interview of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev to the Editor-in-Chief of "New Uzbekistan"
2. Alisher Navoi's work "Mahbubul-qulub".
3. Abdullah Avloni's work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality"

“The first swallow of the East”

Sharipova Shahlo Kholikulovna,

1st year Master’s degree student of the Department of Sculpture, Faculty of Fine Arts, National Institute of Art and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod

Annotation: This article covers the life and work of Tamara, an artist who has left an indelible mark on Uzbek art and culture. At the same time, there was talk of large-scale reforms aimed at developing the activities of the Tamarahonim House Museum.

Keywords: lapar, choreography, drama, stage, music, tour, singing, psyche.

“The history and immortal spirit of the people are reflected in the culture and art, which defines the unique image of each nation and brightly expresses its unique features”¹

Art is an idea, imagination, and emotion that can accurately convey the meaning and purpose of human and human life, as well as direct its activities accordingly.

There are so many nationalities and ethnic groups living on our planet, and regardless of their religion, race, creed, and gender, the concept of art has developed that binds them all together in a certain way, unconditionally understood and accepted. The historical monuments, applied and fine arts, objects of intangible cultural heritage, songs and dances of all peoples, reflecting their national culture and art, are being polished with originality. Within the art forms, dance has a unique magical effect on the human psyche. A special feeling is aroused in your heart when you see a dancer dancing on the stage, moving lightly to the melody of the music. If, the mysterious movements called dance can immerse you in their own world, it is the power of the art of dance.

Dance, like other forms of art, is an artistic way of exploring human life and the entire universe. The emergence of the art of dance goes back a long way. Dance masters who are dedicated to this stage and the dances they create and stage have made a great contribution to the arrival and development of the art of dance. Today we know many famous dancers and enjoy their work. If we look at the history of this field, we can see such dedicated artists as Tamarakhonim.

Tamarakhonim is known not only in our country, but also in the world as one of the founders of the Uzbek national professional art of dance and singing.

Tamara Artemovna Petrosyan was born in 1906 in Skobelev (Turkestan, present-day Uzbekistan). Tamarakhonim’s truly unique talent is reflected in the fact that in each of her lapars, the sweetness of her voice, the charm of her smile, the variety of her clothes are captivating, captivating the audience and each song rises to the level of discovery.

Tamarakhonim was a truly hardworking artist. The hardships of the time did not bend his will. Initially, Mulla Tuychi performed Uzbek folk songs and dances under the pseudonym Sharofatkhan on the advice of Tashmuhamedov.

At the Jar Street Mill Club, he performs at Narkompros concerts with theater artists organized by Ali Ardobus Ibragimov. In the autumn of 1922, he met Muhiddin Qori Yakubov and discovered new aspects of his work. Organizes tours with musicians of Muhiddin Qori Yakubov throughout the cities and villages of the Fergana Valley.

Later, in 1924. In collaboration and under the auspices of Muhiddin Qori Yakubov, he toured Bukhara, Samarkand, Fergana, studied songs, dances, folklore and enriched his repertoire in the regions and districts he visited. The artist, who began to show his art in bird countries, He will go on tour to Baku and sing in Azerbaijani. In 1924 he entered the choreographic department of the Moscow College of Theater Arts under the direction of Vera Maya. "She first appeared on the stage under the pseudonym

¹ “Speech by President Islam Karimov at the Opening Ceremony of the Memorial Complex Dedicated to the 2700th Anniversary of the Book of “Avesto”. “Xalq so’zi” November 6, 2001

Tamarakhonim at the Oriental Evening, organized by leading artists of Moscow theaters.”² The first Minister of Culture of the Soviet state A. Lunacharsky had high hopes for his future in art, calling him “the first swallow of the East.”³ “In 1926, the poet of the fiery revolution, Hamza Hakimzoda Niyazi, wrote a lion dedicated to Tamarakhonim”⁴, "On a tour of England in 1935, he was hailed by the British as the “Pearl of the Orient.”⁵, She was the first woman to appear on the Uzbek stage as a cultural figure.

The fact that the peoples of Central Asia were the first to perform their songs and dances abroad is a clear example of the fact that Tamarakhonim was rightly called “the first swallow of the East.” Tamarakhonim is called a fighting, martial artist.

In our East, the appearance of a woman on the stage with an open face has not only astonished some categories of people, but also aroused strong anger. “The genre I chose requires a combination of music, song, dance and dramatic movement.”⁶, - said the artist. Tamarakhonim won the love of millions by laughing at the world with a fiery and sensitive heart. Halima Nosirova and Mukarrama Turgunbaeva became role models. As the poet Turob Tola said, “Talents inspired by them emerge.”⁷

Born in a remote village to an ordinary working-class family, the artist was able to rise to the top of fame with his talent, hard work and courage. Tamarakhonim contribution to Uzbek culture, song and dance, and her rich artistic heritage have been studied by the younger generation for years. The artist's house-museum began to function during his lifetime. Tamarakhonim Artyomovna's memory is immortalized, and the house where Tamarakhonim lived and worked is now a house museum. It was established as an exhibition of Tamarakhonim's permanent costumes by order of the Ministry of Culture No. 16 of January 16, 1986.

By order of the Ministry of Culture No. 42 of June 14, 1994, Tamarakhonim's permanent costume exhibition was transformed into Tamarakhonim 's house museum. Anyone who has visited the house-museum will be convinced that the legacy left by Tamarakhonim is a whole school of life and creativity. When we look at the museum halls, we see Tamarakhonim's clothes in Fergana, Bukhara, Margilan, Khorezm, Tajik, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkmen and Uyghur clothes of the neighboring republic. And we can see many examples of different, unique costumes of the peoples of the world. It is hand-embroidered with silk, satin, velvet by masters and filled with jewelry.

Every detail in it is a perfect example of art. Among the visitors to the museum today, we meet many young dancers, musicians, folk masters and ethnographic ensembles who are just entering the art.

It is safe to say that such museums, which serve as a bridge between history and the future, serve as a great school of creativity for young talents. Due to the great attention paid by the President to the development of museums, a lot of work is being done at the Tamara House Museum.

In this regard, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 28, 2018 PQ No.4038 on the approval of the Concept of further development of national culture is a clear example of this.

List of used references:

1. “Speech of President Islam Karimov at the opening ceremony of the memorial complex dedicated to the 2700th anniversary of the book” Avesto”. “Xalq so’zi” November 6, 2001 №226 (2788) 2 pages
2. Archive of Tamarakhonim House-Museum
3. “Tojikiston of Soviet” 10.07.1991 №123 (18.405) Z. Zulfiqorov
4. Archive of Tamarakhonim house-museum (manuscripts)

² Archive of Tamarakhonim House Museum

³ Tojikiston of Soviet 10.07.1991 №123 (18.405) Z. Zulfiqorov

⁴ Archive of Tamarakhonim House Museum

⁵ Archive of Tamarakhonim House Museum

⁶ Tamarakhonim House Museum Archive (manuscripts)

⁷ Archive of Tamarakhonim House Museum

“Psychology of self-development ”

Sadirxonova Shoista Abidjanova
Toshkent Davlat Sharqshunoslik
Universiteti akademik litseyi
oila psixologiyasi fani o`qituvchisi

Annotation: The beginning of self-development or the beginning of self-development? In this article, let's define such self-development, ways of self-development, and what methods of self-development begin with.

Key words: self-improvement, results, individual, developing and improving, environment, Psychology, motivation.

Self-development is a difficult process, final in the stages of creating a personal life. Sooner or later, it comes mainly because of the protest, because of the self-dissatisfaction, the familiarity with the example of the individual and the society around him. Fear is put on the weak person, so it is subject to emotions, not against him. But not against, not wrong. Rather, it means being individual, developing and improving. To achieve this, you need to constantly work on yourself, because self-improvement is not a privilege. It's impossible to transfer all your energy to one area of life, let's just say with your head down and do it in the morning just to make money. We need to start making changes in every little bit of life, in small steps, so you can get results. Self-development is a path that must go through certain stages of development. To start, get to know yourself, define your life in your life, and be amazed that you are in this world. Then you need to set your goals where you want to work, what results you want to achieve. They should be short-term, not only for the long term, but to get the result permanently, then the stimulation of the stimulus will intensify. The next stage plan is a spreadsheet, the results you need to dream about and the steps you need to take to achieve your dream, to achieve, to achieve the result. After all, once you take a step, you will gather the strength of will and not rest along the way. The results may be surprising, but they say it's not in vain, but that he is capable of more than he thinks. Many scientists have been studying ways of self-improvement for a long time, and many of them need to be considered in more detail. Most importantly, choose priorities, first of all understand what is important and in what direction to move. Most scientists don't have a set time or plan in their plans, it all depends on priorities. "Here and now." Understand the principle. Often, a normal and frustrated world leads to reality, which requires you to understand where you are and what you are doing.

Focus. Usually when we play something, thinking takes us out of things, as a result the work goes on for a long time, but there is no sense of thoughts. Or a person is cooking dinner and at the same time he is cooking in parallel to the TV, usually for a longer period of time than the burning fire, or worse. In this case, self-control helps. When you start to lose consciousness, start wanting to go out on something, you need to understand yourself and stop, go back to work. By focusing on the task, you can not only achieve it faster, but also increase its efficiency.

Plan your day. We need to find time for all areas of life. Correct smart ideas. In this case, it is better to create a notebook and write down some ideas and thoughts or to write down all the ideas and thoughts to achieve the goals. Thanks to this method, the brain starts looking for ways and eventually gives you a lot of advice on what to do. Control time because it is the most valuable, non-renewable resource. Here is the perfect time to manage your time properly, plan your time properly and spend your time, as well as save time for local networks, unreasonable experiences, unreasonable experiences, unreasonable experiences and going back to the past.

Change the environment. Communicate with people who can be tested, teach them something new I'm looking for. Don't listen to the advice of people who have achieved nothing in this area, but just know how to speak beautifully. And limit contact by lowering and constantly complaining. Walk forward. Even small steps lead to great results.

Go for a goal through stress. Interesting, but the reality is a stressful situation Most people are motivated and can also get out of their comfort zone.

Start moving

Self-improvement is a great way to understand yourself and a great way to achieve the results you set. Everyone is able to create as they wish, because there are no restrictions. Most importantly, set goals and actions.

The beginning of self-development and personal growth: the first steps (video) What to do to start self-improvement:

Reading time 6 minutes

Psychology of self-development is concerned with the formation of personality and character, the development of habits and social reactions. Without it, it is impossible to hand over the “new world” man who entered the age of information. Self-development means “moving in different directions to achieve new goals, to set new tasks to achieve goals. and you will learn what factors influence its overall development.

Psychology of self-improvement is a difficult subject that cannot be understood for hours or days. Sometimes, being aware of this experience is left to other people, to understand and accept the person in themselves.

In order to properly respect situations and be on the path to development, it is necessary to understand the basic mental processes that help a person understand the world around them.

Basic mental processes:

- memory;
- emotion;
- thinking;
- attention;
- imagination;
- speech.

These processes are distinguished by the display of the person interacting with the outside world. Development depends on its level. According to them, it is possible to assess how much a person has developed. The main process is memory, which has the property to memorize important information that will be needed in the future. There are people with well-developed memory and they don't need medication. There are several other ways to improve the quality of memory. Personal development is an important part of family life and career. And the additional skills that help you achieve your goals will help you increase your level. Another situation is that he is completely phlegmatic all around and has no personal growth. It will be boring not only for others but for himself as well. No one is stagnant, and no one can give anything new to this development, and more and more, no one is at risk of this “innovation”.

Psychology self-development

Everyone is inherent in nature, he can be strong or weak. The psychology of self-development is in development and even in characteristic evolution, resulting in a person leading to a goal or a secret dream. The main enemy of personality development can be poor physical and moral health. Not a gift, they say in a healthy mind in a healthy body, because our problems, disorders and minor problems affect the condition of the internal organs. There is no health. Anxiety slows down a person's development, it is necessary to refuse contact with the outside world during the illness. Such problems need to be addressed, whether they lead you to the zero point of the segment or bring science abroad to your knowledge. This will not happen, it is necessary to define the concept of self-development from the point of view of psychology and implement it. This process of self-improvement, it is constant, can lead to irreversible consequences in its history, including: life-oriented, indifference, sadness, depression, depression, depression, depression. A person who is dissatisfied with his life tries to cover his shortcomings with constant silence over the rest. In a great community, it is possible to observe the formation of personalities such as gossip groups that do not suffer evil and eternal suffering. An unpleasant sight, isn't it?

Therefore, from the point of view of the psychology of self-development, it is necessary to fully reveal the subject of the inner happiness of the individual and emphasize the impossibility, 3 main points.

1. Motivation

Without it, one cannot achieve one's goals, but simply sits and waits. If there is career motivation, in a relationship it leads to positive results.

2. result

At this point, it deserves special attention. Without it, no new goals will emerge, without which a person will be limited by the opinions of his fellow believers or someone else, resulting in a universal misconception.

3. Self-development plan

Properly structured step-by-step instructions are on the way to happiness. Going to your goals doesn't focus on the obstacles in life - it allows you to systematize your desires and aspirations while encouraging the wills.

Reference:

1. Warfield.Ru - Psychology of modernity - family.
2. Relationships. Tips for a psychologist. Business conversation

Environmental sensing and its role in achieving strategic agility Analytical descriptive research in the Iraqi South Oil Company

Mustafa Sabah Hlehel¹

Department of Public Administration / College of Administration and Economics / Sumer University:
mmss225580mu@gmail.com

Tariq Kazem Shalaka²

Department of Public Administration / College of Administration and Economics / University of Sumer/E-tareq81202@gmail.com

Abstract: -The purpose of the research is to measure the role of environmental sensing processes in achieving strategic lightness, based on the descriptive-analytical approach, as the intellectual and philosophical framework for this research was formed through the interaction of two variables (environmental sensing, strategic lightness), and to understand and clarify this framework, the essential dimensions of sensing were adopted. The environment is represented by survey, monitoring, forecasting, evaluation. As for the dimensions of strategic lightness, it was embodied in strategic sensitivity, strategic response, and strategic capabilities. A sample of (82) employees of the South Oil Company was surveyed, and this research sought to answer several questions from During the presentation of the theoretical philosophy and the intellectual implications of these variables, this is in addition to what was reached through the field side of the research in which it was relied on to design a questionnaire form whose paragraphs fit with the nature of the research environment, which was represented in a sample of the workers of the South Oil Company, and the research came out with several conclusions In the light of which several recommendations were raised for the research sample company, and one of the most important conclusions reached by this research is that environmental sensing has an active role No, and a significant impact on achieving the company's strategic agility

Keywords: Environmental sensing, strategic agility, the South Oil Company / Iraq

Introduction

The problem of the continuity of organizations working in their environment is one of the problems that are looking for solutions and that occupied the thinking of researchers in the field of organization management, strategic management, and managers of public and private organizations alike. Very complex environmental conditions and dynamic changes that characterize the Iraqi work environment, as it has been exposed, two decades ago, to abnormal conditions that have affected the existence and work of organizations in general, so the researcher chose the topic of research because of the real threats these organizations suffer and based on the importance and seriousness of these Threats to which these organizations are exposed This research came to explain the importance and impact of the environmental sensing process by employing its indicators (survey, monitoring, evaluation, prediction) in achieving the vision and mission of the organization in reaching strategic lightness.

Research problem

The topic of environmental sensing plays an active role in the life cycle of all organizations, regardless of the size and nature of the activity. Changes and developments and their translation for the benefit of the organization, and this is done through the important information obtained by the organization resulting from sensing its environment and monitoring the movement of external variables to collect and communicate information to and from the organization. In light of this, the research problem was identified by raising the

following main question: (Does the South Oil Company realize the role of sensing operations for its work environment in achieving strategic lightness?) and the following questions are branched from it:-

- 1- What is the level of interest of the SoC in environmental sensing operations?
 - 2- Do environmental sensing operations contribute to achieving the strategic success of the research sample company?
 - 3- What is the nature of the relationship and impact between environmental sensing operations and indicators of strategic lightness, the South Oil Company?
- research assumes

In light of the research problem, the researcher puts two main hypotheses, as follows:

The first main hypothesis: There is no significant correlation between environmental sensing and its operations with strategic success in its dimensions.

The second main hypothesis: There is no significant effect of environmental sensing processes on achieving success Strategic dimensions.

Strategic sensing concept

(1967: 165, Thompson) referred to the term environmental sensing for the first time, as a way to adapt to the external environment to protect the technical core of the organization. And organizations outside the boundaries of its organization (Hodge & Anthony, 2003: 111) and (Raghu & Vinze, 2005: 1-5) indicated that the process of environmental sensing must be managed through an appropriate combination of (technology, skills, and knowledge) to ensure the success of the organization in an environment of uncertainty. (2005:43, Dess et al.) explained that environmental sensing includes monitoring the external environment of organizations to predict environmental changes from their sources and predict current changes under any direction, and successful environmental sensing warns the organization of critical trends and events before those changes develop and realize their risks. And before competitors distinguish it, environmental sensing embodies patterns of activities for a group or organization that are developed over some time, so that the organization can develop its competencies in the face of the risks of environmental uncertainty, so it needs to make more efforts to support its ability and skill in environmental sensing At the internal and external level (Levina & Vaast 2006:13, so it is a set of activities that occur within the internal and external borders of the organization to maintain the level of interaction in the relationship of the organization with the surrounding environment (Hustad & Bechina, 2012: 122), and indicates (7:2013). Often, environmental sensing is a creative approach that provides the organizational process with new information about the environment by linking the organization with its environment, which facilitates the flow of information between the environment and the organization and ultimately leads to the strengthening of the process interaction between them. In light of the foregoing, researchers believe that environmental sensing is a continuous, dynamic process of paramount importance to all business organizations, regardless of the size and nature of the activity, as it guarantees them the ability to read the future and seize the opportunities available in it and enhance their capabilities in the face of expected risks, enabling them to survive and grow in a world its own business.

Dimensions of strategic sensing:-

Survey: Surveys refer to surveying the environment in general to discover ongoing environmental change and to identify signs of potential environmental change. Before formulating the strategy, the senior management examines the external environment to identify potential opportunities and threats, and often the information obtained by the organization through examinations The environment is ambiguous, incomplete, or unconnected (2001:41, Hitt et al. The senior management is responsible for analyzing the data and giving it the exact meaning and transforming that data into information that can benefit the organization. The survey is an important activity because it includes identifying the variables of the influencing factors and collecting them in a consistent manner Between the external and internal environment (Salman et al., 2021: 74)

Monitoring and measurement: It is the organized process of tracking environmental events and fluctuations discovered through survey operations, as analysts, through monitoring operations, confirm their intuition about the environmental signals and changes in the previous stage and sort the data that constitute an important element in this stage and set aside some data that the analyst sees as unrelated to the events and the

changes being measured. At this stage, the organization determines the impact of these factors on it. It focuses on the factors that it believes have a significant impact on the organization's activity (1993:24Narayanan & Nath.)

Forecasting: (Salman et al., 2021: 74) indicates that the forecasting strategy is based on the necessity of research and field survey of market requirements, identifying fluctuations in demand for products and services, and developing appropriate solutions for them. Harem (2003: 190) emphasizes that the forecasting strategy enables the organization to have the necessary resources available, as well as to anticipate the demand for products, the organization's plans. It shows that if it is difficult to control environmental fluctuations through reservation or grading, the organization resorts to predicting or anticipating changes in the conditions of supply and demand and adapting to them, as the organization can anticipate and then prepare for the variables that cannot be reserved or gradual (Dagher and Saleh, 2000: 132 If accurate forecasting is possible, the technical core of the organization can be protected and its performance is preserved (Jackson et al., 1988: 132). It is possible to prepare for the impact on the environment by making some adjustments to preserve the technical essence, such as postponing expansion plans and canceling non-productive units when anticipating difficult days, anticipating some shifts in supply and demand, and preparing for these surprises (Thompson, 1967:164).

Evaluation: Its objective is to determine the timing and importance of the impact of the environmental factors that resulted from the survey, measurement, and forecasting processes. Analysts can understand the environment through their large data on the environment but without a clear correlation or relationship regarding where the effects will be harmful to the organization or represent opportunities that must be Their investment and that the evaluation process enables them to decipher the puzzle, understand the interconnectedness and clearly define the relationship between environmental and organizational factors (Salman and others, 2021: 75).

The concept of strategic agility

The origin of strategic agility as a concept in business can be traced back to Flexible Manufacturing Systems (FMS) Initially the path to manufacturing flexibility was thought to be through automation to enable rapid change (eg reduced set-up times) and thus greater responsiveness to changes in product mix and volume (Aitken, 2002). :2) The term light manufacturing was coined by a U.S. government-sponsored research program at Lehigh University, at the Iacocca Institute in 1991 (Bennett & Katayama 2012: 227), (Oyedijo, 1999:2) to describe a flexible manufacturing system that has the capabilities necessary to meet the rapidly changing needs of the market and can respond to the requirements of customers promptly (Nematizadeh & Khoshnood 2017: 221) in response to the request of the US Congress to prepare a report on the strategy of industrial organizations in the twenty-first century, the report emphasized that the current system of mass production was not sufficient to ensure Improvement and help organizations keep pace with the competition, especially Japanese manufacturing organizations, which were characterized by their flexibility, and this, in turn, requires a new system of production (Sethi, 2004: 18. It seems that manufacturing organizations reinforced the concept of lightness within organizations By the mid-nineties of the twentieth century, the largest American organizations, especially in the information technology and telephony sectors, adopted the concept of lightness (Young, 2013:5), and in the period after (2000) the trend towards studying lightness from an organizational perspective (Wendle, 2013: 150) He stated (2016:3) (Najrani) that the presence of Khuffa is not limited to business only but also, in government, non-profit bodies, schools, universities and all classes of organizations. With the expansion of the horizons of organizations and the development of their future direction and the service of their strategic direction, the term agility was adopted as a strategic direction for it, and the efforts of the Finnish researchers (Kozonen & Doz) were among those endeavors, and despite the adoption of the concept of agility in many of their researches, they raised the term "strategic agility." In their book (Fast Strategy) in 2008, and it appeared in their research on this topic (Audran, 2011:47) and became a description of strategic agility as the ability to continuously adjust and adapt to the strategic direction in the core business, creating not only new products and services but also new business models and innovative ways to create value for the organization (Teoh, 2017:223) Therefore, the literature and studies provide different perspectives on strategic leanness or manufacturing leanness research. It is not surprising to see that the

concept of leanness has been defined in different ways in the literature (Beh, 2007:34) sees (245: 2003, Sambamurthy et al.) It includes the exploration and exploitation of opportunities, exploration is the experimentation with new alternatives and the pursuit of knowledge about currently unknown opportunities for competitive action, and exploitation is the use and development of things already known through the refinement and expansion of existing competencies, technologies and knowledge Pinsonneault & Tallon (2011: 473) defined strategic agility as referring to the speed with which organizations can detect and respond to opportunities and environmental threats. Bouwman et al. (2017:2) describe it as a concept applied in organizational theory and industrialization to It is the ability to adapt and respond to change and uncertainty, related to policy, regulation or regulation, the market, competing for behavior, or fundamental technological changes. (Allwein, 2017: 35) introduced another concept in which he indicated that it is “an expression of what individuals do or achieve, not what they can do or the capabilities they possess” and that these shifts focus on the practices in the organization while holding (Al-Amri and Hussein, 2018: 5) that strategic agility is the ability of organizations to deal with changes in the business environment through Gaining strategic thinking to adapt to these sudden changes accurately, quickly and in a way that is ahead of competitors, which helps the organization to maximize its strengths, and thus achieve a good competitive position in the market designed to meet the changing needs and desires of customers.

Dimensions of strategic agility

Strategic sensitivity: Strategic sensitivity represents both the intensity of awareness, the intensity of awareness and attention, that is, it combines early and acute awareness of trends in the environment with a strong, real-time sense of strategic situations as they develop and emerge (Doz & Kosonen, 2008b: 96). To anticipate future trends and the direction of areas of work that need strong intuition (Mace, 2016:41) and this requires organizations to be open to as much information, intelligence and innovations as possible by creating and maintaining relationships with different people and different organizations (Santala, 2009: 46) It is also the ability of organizations to actively seek to collect usable data, absorb this data and filter the appropriate ones, accurately and in a timely manner, to be able to anticipate or detect opportunities and threats in the business environment (Mavengere, 2013:11) and strategic sensitivity is a combination of foresight foresight, insight and simple investigations, with the utmost importance for foresight (Al-Amri and Hussain, 2018: 150) foresight consists of a set of techniques, practices, and processes that Organizations serve them to discover new events and changes in their external environment, explore their evolution and potential impacts, and determine response options (Vecchiato, 2014:2), that is, perceiving, learning and anticipating trends in the evolving business environment and depends extensively on pattern awareness, which is the quality that the expert in a game possesses. Chess can see a lot of forwarding moves, while the opponent sees only a little less, and foresight is only as good as the ability to understand and plan an environment and anticipate its development (Doz & Kosonen, 2008:7). Insight is awareness, analysis, and understanding of complex strategic situations, and when they develop, they are ready to take advantage of them (Mavengere, 2013:11). True strategic insight means looking for new trends and innovations even when they are not supported by the current strategy and require radical changes (Santa, 47: 2009).

Strategic response: The strategic response represents the organization's ability to quickly and smoothly reconfigure its resources and operations in cooperation with its customers and partners as a response or anticipate change and consists of an internal response orientation, and an external response orientation (Mavengere, 2013:11) "External response orientation" has been analyzed into proactive and reactionary For the business environment, as for the “internal response” orientation, it was analyzed to resource fluidity and business process maturity. Resource fluidity is related to the rapid redistribution of resources and the reconfiguration of business systems after considering the internal capabilities. As for the process maturity, it is the effectiveness and control of the chain of work activities in the organization and the possibility of Forecasting it (14:2013 (Mavengere Phys. 96:20) Doz & Kosonen describes resource liquidity as the internal ability to rapidly reconfigure business systems and redistribute resources based on organizational processes, resource allocation, people management approaches, mechanisms, and incentives, and thus allow the organization to organize and launch Expanding the scope and implementing new growth initiatives and new businesses may make its core business more resilient. (Al-Amri and Hussain, 2018: 151) divided it into three

main groups; Mobilizing capital resources, which means enhancing resources in a way that enables them to absorb changes in the environment and has an impact on the direction of development, mobilizing people and knowledge that contributes to the reallocation of scarce resources, creating models for structures that allow facilitating the reallocation of resources through reusable systems and processes that help organizations To reduce risks related to the start of new business. As for (2015:17, Weichert Tautermann &) sees that the strategic response includes three capabilities; Speed refers to the ability to cover needs quickly, reactivity refers to how quickly needs can be identified, and visibility refers to capturing events promptly. That is, it is concerned with the availability of liquidity, resources, and capabilities in the internal business systems and the rapid reconfiguration and redistribution of resources (Al-Amri and Hussein, 2018: 150).

Collaborative capabilities: The organization can benefit from the integration of all its resources, for example, information, employees, functions, infrastructure, and partners, and represents a comprehensive dimension of strategic agility and consists of all basic organizational capabilities that are not classified within strategic sensitivity and strategic response (Mavengere, 2013: 12-14), the value of cooperation and integration leads to organizational empowerment, because it makes it more informed, more flexible and responsive to changing customer needs and enables it to make quick decisions. Focusing on the top-down role, however, others have since argued that the term ignores the distributed role of leadership, seeing the unity of command as only one determinant of the team's higher ability to reach collective commitments. Thus, group commitment is a common ground, Shared interest, empathy, and trust to increase the participation of members of the organization. Collaboration between senior management and working in coordination with colleagues enhances the performance of the management team through the development of constructive dialogue and, most importantly, the leadership style of the CEO, that enables the organization to achieve maximum diversified results and form a harmonious management team (Pesonen, 2009: 16). Collaboration and teamwork are very important characteristics of light organizations, when properly implemented, teams lead to the emergence of different viewpoints, which can greatly improve the creation process and the organization's ability to adapt to change. But for these opinions to be effective, team members' views must be channeled through clear, goal-oriented dialogue to avoid any loudly motivated decisions (2011:41, Audran)

The practical side:-

Research hypothesis testing

The researchers adopted a set of statistical methods to test the hypotheses that emerged from the research, as follows:

1- There is no significant correlation between environmental sensing in its dimensions and strategic lightness in its dimensions. Table (1) indicates the results of the correlation relations (Speannan between variables, and it is clear from it that there are positive correlations between them, but they were fluctuating in terms of their statistical significance, and as follows: following:

Table (1) shows the correlation matrix, arithmetic means, and standard deviations of the research variables.

Dimensions	mean	standard deviation	strategic sensitivity	strategic response	cooperative ability	strategic agility
scanning	3.59	0.64	0.286*	0.076	0.004	0.104
Monitoring and measuring	3.58	0.79	0.159**	0.152	0.118	0.149
Forecasting	3.42	0.75	0.333**	0.364**	0.485**	0.478**
Evaluation	3.41	0.78	0.429**	0.471**	0.332**	0.468**
environmental sensing	3.50	0.55	0.467**	0.409**	0.355**	0.470**
Arithmetic mean			3.46	3.54	3.51	3.50
standard deviation			0.64	0.72	0.84	0.59

**Significant at the level (1%) * Significant at the level (5%)

According to Table (1), the survey's relationship with strategic sensitivity was significant at level (5), while it was not significant with the rest of the dimensions as well as at the overall level. The control relationship was

not significant with any of the dimensions of strategic lightness, and the relationship of both prediction and evaluation was positive and significant with the dimensions of strategic lightness at the sub- and macro levels. At the macro level, the environmental sensing variable achieved statistical and significant correlation relationships at the sub- and macro levels with the strategic agility variable.

The researcher infers from the possibility of the South Oil Company benefiting from the environmental sensing operations available to it to enhance its strategic agility. Accordingly, the researchers inferred the rejection of the above hypothesis in part.

2- There is no significant effect of environmental sensing in achieving strategic lightness in its dimensions.

To test the above hypothesis, the researchers used multiple regression and the (Stepwise) method, which is a statistically efficient method as it identifies the variables most influential in the dependent variable, as follows:

- The dimensions of environmental sensing do not affect the dimension of strategic sensitivity.

Table (2) below shows the above hypothesis testing using the Stepwise method) where both the survey and observation dimensions were omitted, and the analysis settled on the prediction and evaluation dimensions as follows:

Table (2) Testing the first sub-effect hypothesis using the Stepwise method

dependent variable independent variable	strategic sensitivity		Calculated t value	computed f value	R ²
	α	β			
Forecasting	1.85	0.225	**3.32	**11.65	0.24
Evaluation		0.245	**2.71		

**Significant at the level (1%)

It is evident from the above table that:

1- Prediction affects survival by (0.225) if it changes by one unit, and this is a positive and significant effect at the (1%) level because the calculated f value was significant at the mentioned level.

2 - The evaluation affects survival by (0.245) if it changes by one unit, which is a positive and moral effect at the level of (1%). Because the calculated f) value was significant at the mentioned level.

3- The value off), which measures the significance of the regression model, reached its value (11.65), which is a significant value at the level of (1%).

4- The value of the coefficient of determination (R) was (0.24), which means that the two dimensions of prediction and evaluation explain the amount of (24%) of the changes that occur in the survival dimension, and the remaining percentage is due to other factors not included in the model. This is what the researcher infers to reject the above hypothesis by (50%).

- The dimensions of environmental sensing do not affect the dimension of the strategic response.

Table (3) below shows the above hypothesis test using the Stepwise method, where both the survey and observation dimensions were omitted, and the analysis settled on the two dimensions of prediction and evaluation, as follows:

Table (3) Testing the second sub-hypothesis using (Stepwise) method

independent variable \ dependent variable	strategic response		Calculated t value	computed f value	R ²
	α	β			
Forecasting	1.76	0.28	**3.73	**12.34	0.26
Evaluation		0.24	**2.45		

**Significant at the level (1%)

It is evident from the above table that:

1- The prediction affects the strategic response by an amount of (0.28) if it changes by one unit, and this is a positive and significant effect at the level (1%) because the calculated f value was significant at the mentioned level.

2- The evaluation affects adaptation by (0.24) if it changes by one unit, which is a positive and moral effect at the level of (1%). Because the calculated f) value was significant at the mentioned level.

3- The value of (f), which measures the significance of the regression model, reached its value (12.34), which is a significant value at the level of (1%).

4- The value of the coefficient of determination (R) was (0.26), which means that the prediction and evaluation dimensions explain the amount of (26) changes that occur in the strategic response dimension, and the remaining percentage is due to other factors not included in the model. The researchers inferred the rejection of the above hypothesis by (50%).

• The dimensions of environmental sensing do not affect the dimension of strategic capability.

Table (4) below shows the above hypothesis testing using the (Stepwise) method, where both were omitted after the survey

The analysis settled on the two dimensions of prediction and evaluation, as follows:

Table (4) Testing the third sub-hypothesis effect using the (Stepwise) method.

independent variable \ dependent variable	strategic ability		Calculated t value	computed f value	R ²
	α	β			
Forecasting	1.21	0.48	**3.81	**13.75	0.28
Evaluation		0.25	**2.72		

**Significant at the level (1%)

It is evident from the above table that:

1- The prediction affects the strategic ability by 0.48 if it changes by one unit, and this is a positive and significant effect at the (1%) level because the calculated (f) value was significant at the mentioned level.

2- The evaluation affects the strategic ability by (0.25) if it changes by one unit, which is a positive and moral effect at the level of (1%). Because the calculated (f) value was significant at the mentioned level.

3- The value of (f), which measures the significance of the regression model, reached its value (13.75), which is a significant value at the level of (1%).

4- The value of the coefficient of determination (R) reached (0.28), which means that the two dimensions of prediction and evaluation explain the amount of (28%) of the changes that occur in the dimension of strategic ability, and the remaining percentage is due to other factors not included in the model. The researchers inferred the rejection of the above hypothesis by (50%).

Conclusions and Recommendations:-

This topic deals with the conclusions and recommendations that were reached according to the field side of the study, as follows:

Conclusions

The results of describing the opinions of the research sample showed a great interest in environmental sensing operations, and the survey process ranked first in the interests of the research sample, which indicates that it works on identifying the first signals and following them up on changes in the general environment and its trends by developing a complete perception of the external environment, as well as showing its interest in the second degree, the monitoring process, which indicates that the management of the South Oil Company is working on analyzing the external environment as a means of evaluating environmental trends, following up on events and scheduling activities by systematically examining the development of environmental changes to identify opportunities and warn against threats, as well as tracking the behavior of customers and competitors' activities. The prediction process is ranked third, as this indicates that the research sample company is working to develop acceptable trends about the direction, extent, speed, and strength of environmental changes around the company, to know the expected changes in the external environment, which helps in identifying opportunities and threats and evaluating future environmental factors in preparation for determining the appropriate behavior to deal with them. , while the evaluation process ranked fourth among the company's interests in the research sample, which indicates It realizes the importance of determining the timing of environmental changes and their importance and directions on strategic management through surveys, monitoring, and forecasting to determine the interdependence and relationship between its internal factors and the external environment. The statistical results also showed the existence of a significant correlation between environmental sensing operations and strategic lightness, which confirms that the company is interested in the research sample with survey operations because of its positive relationship to obtaining resources and capabilities that allow it to develop its competitive advantage. As well as the interest of the Southern Oil Company in monitoring operations, as it has a positive relationship with providing a level of protection that provides it with the necessary information because of the changes and events around it that may determine its success now or in the future.

The results also indicated that the South Oil Company uses forecasting processes for its positive relationship to the lightness of the company in the future as a result of what it predicts regarding its future environment and the opportunities or threats it will face or avoid in the future. The company also relies on the evaluation process for its positive relationship to achieving a high level of efficiency and effectiveness, which results in Information outputs that serve as inputs to the process of making strategic decisions. The statistical results showed that there is a significant effect of environmental sensing processes on strategic lightness through the significant impact of the forecasting process in building the strategic lightness of the company. The research sample came first in terms of impact, and it is a process that provides information and knowledge about what will affect the environment and work to avoid it or confront it. It came in second place in terms of the impact of the evaluation process. The research sample company deliberately evaluated the information it obtained to indicate its validity, auditing, and classification according to importance and delivery to decision-makers, while the monitoring process ranked third in terms of impact. This indicates that the research sample companies are constantly monitoring their environment R to prepare for it and adapt to it.

Recommendations: -

In light of the foregoing study of the impact of environmental sensing and strategic lightness in its theoretical aspect, and the results of field analyzes, the current research reached a set of recommendations that contribute to building strategic lightness by activating environmental sensing processes for the research sample companies in particular and business organizations in general, and my agencies The focus is on the

practice of environmental sensing operations in the South Oil Company more broadly in light of the environment of Iraq, which is characterized by change and environmental uncertainty by constantly doing the following:

The external environment, which gives it the advantage of identifying changes that threaten its existence and opportunities that, if invested, will help it to fortify its competitive position with the Iraqi consumer, by monitoring the external environment, enabling it to compare what it owns with its competitors to identify its market position and maintain its market share in the Iraqi environment. And predicting the external environment to reveal what it contains future opportunities and threats to adopt or adapt to them with the capabilities and capabilities it has that enable it to sustain its current success. Working on evaluating the external environment through the information it collected, classifying it, classifying it, and communicating it to decision-makers faster than it can outperform competitors. Strengthening the company's resources and capabilities at all levels in a way that competitors find it difficult to overcome by searching for new resources that help it sustain the production wheel, which does not allow it to stop as a result of the lack of basic resources for production operations, as well as developing its capabilities and capabilities at all levels, whether they are production, service or marketing To advance the Iraqi product inside the country with its future development to obtain the ISO 9001 certificate with the possibility of marketing it outside the country, and to identify modern technology that contributes to the speed of production and meeting the needs of the local market in the required quantities by raising the production capacity, which increases its profits and market share compared to what is imported from outside Country.

Sources:

1. Salman, Fatma Abdul Ali and Al-Shammari, Muhammad Awad Jarallah and Al-Shamry, Ahmed Abdullah Amanah, (2021) "The Impact of Environmental Sensing Operations in Enhancing Strategic Success Indicators" Journal of Management and Economics, Vol. 10, No. 37.
2. Thompson, John, L., (1997) Strategic Management: Awareness and Change 3rd ed., Hall pub., The United States of America.
3. Jackson, John Haze, Cyril L. Morgano Joseph J. And Badilo (1988), "Organization Theory: A Holistic Perspective to Management", translated by Khaled Hassan Marzouk, Saudi Arabia Library.
4. Munqith Muhammad Dagher, and Adel Harhoush Salih (2000) "The Theory of Organization and Organizational Behavior" Dar Al-Kutub for Printing, Baghdad, Iraq.
5. Hussein, Harem (2003) Organizations Management", first edition, Dar Al-Hamid for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
6. Narayanan Veeay., & Nath Rachu .,(1993) "Organization Theory": A Strategic Approach, Irwin McGraw-Hill book Co, United States of America 1993.
7. Hitt, Michael., Ireland, R& Hoskisson, R,(2001) Strategic Management Competitiveness and Globalization, Southwestern College Pub., United Kingdom,
8. Hustad , Eli, & Aurilla Aurelie Bechina. (2012), "Exploring the Role of Boundary Spanning in Distributed Networks of Knowledge." Electronic Journal of Knowledge Management 10.2, p.10.
9. Ofstein, Laurel F. (2013), " Boundary Spanning in the Entrepreneurial Firm: Effects on Innovation and Firm Performance". Doctor Dissertation, Diss. DePaul University.
10. Levina, N., and Vaast, E. (2005), "The emergence of boundary spanning competence in practice: implications for implementation and use of information systems," MIS Quarterly (29:2).
11. Dess, Gregory G.; Lumpkin, G.T. & Eisner, Alan B., (2005)" Strategic Management: Text and Cases " 2nd Edition, McGraw- Hill, New York,
12. Raghu, T.S., & Vinze, A.(2005) "A business process context for Knowledge Management" Decision Support Systems,
13. Hodge, Billy J; William P. Anthony & Lawrence M. Gales, (2003), "Organization Theory: A Strategic Approach", 6th ed, Person Education, Inc., New Jersey, U.S.A.

14. Aitken, James; Christopher, Martin & Towill, Denis, (2002)," Understanding, Implementing and Exploiting Agility and Leanness", International Journal of Logistics Research & Application, Vol 5. No. 1, 59-74.
15. Katayama, Hiroshi. & Bennett, David, (1999), "Agility, adaptability, and leanness: A comparison of concepts and a study of practice", Int. J. Production Economics, Vol. 60-61, 59-74.
16. Oyedijo, Ade, (2012), "Strategic Agility and Competitive Performance in the Nigerian Telecommunication Industry: An Empirical Investigation", American International Journal of Contemporary Research, Vol. 2, No. 3.
17. Khoshnood, Nikoo Tabe & Nematizadeh, Sina, (2017), " Strategic Agility and Its Impact on the Competitive Capabilities in Iranian Private Banks", International Journal of Business and Management, Vol. 12, No. 2.
18. Sethi, Mukesh Chander A/L Kidarnath, (2004), " Factors influencing Agility in Supply chain management -A preliminary investigation in the electronics industry of Northern Malaysia. "Doctor Dissertation of Business Administration(Unpublished), International Graduate School of Management Division of Business and Enterprise, University of South Australia.
19. Young Alethea G, (2013)," Identifying the impact of leadership practices of Organizational Agility", Master Thesis in Science of Organization Development(Unpublished), The George L. Graziadio School of Business and Management, Pepperdine University, United States.
20. Wendler, Roy, (2013), "Informatyka Ekonomiczna Business Informatics ",1th Edition, House of Wroclaw University of Economics, Germany.
21. Najrani, Majed (2016)," The Effect of Change Capability, Learning Capability and Shared Leadership on Organizational Agility", Doctor Dissertation of Education in Organizational Leadership(Unpublished), Pepperdine University.
22. Audran, Arthur, (2011), Strategic Agility: A Winning Phenotype in Turbulent Environments, Master Thesis in Science of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering(Unpublished), Politecnico Di Milano.
23. Teoh, A. P.; Lee, K.Y.& Muthuveloo, R.,(2017), " The Impact of Enterprise Risk Management, Strategic Agility, and Quality of Internal Audit Function on Firm Performance", International Review of Management and Marketing, Vol. 7, No. 1, 222-229.
24. Beh, Kok, Khim, (2007)," Strategic Agility in The Semiconductor Industry in Malaysia & Singapore", Doctor Dissertation of Philosophy in the Faculty of Humanities (Unpublished), The University of Manchester of Business School.
25. Overby, E., Bharadwaj, A., Sambamurthy, V., (2005)," A framework for enterprise agility and the enabling role of digital options", IFIP International Federation for Information Processing, vol. 180. Springer, pp. 295–312
26. Tallon, P. P. & Pinsonneault, A.,(2011)," Competing Perspectives on the Link between Strategic Information Technology Alignment and Organizational Agility: Insights from a Mediation Model", MIS Quarterly, Vol.35, No.2, 463-486.
27. Bouwman, Harry ; Heikkilä, Jukka ; Heikkilä, Marikka; Leopold, Carlo & Haaker, Timber, (2017), " Achieving agility using business model stress testing ", cross mark, Springerlink.com.
28. Allwein, Florian, (2017), "The role of digital infrastructures in performances of organizational agility", Doctor Thesis of Philosophy in Management (Unpublished), The London School of Economics and Political Science.
29. Doz, Y. & Kosounen, M., (2008a), "Fast Strategy", Wharton Scholl, Publishing, Harlow.
30. Mace, Richard, (2016), " Business Model Innovation, Business Model Enablers, and The Strategic Agility Paradox, Doctor Dissertation of Business Administration(Unpublished), Capella University.
31. Santala, Maarit, (2009), Strategic Agility in a Small Knowledge-Intensive Business Services Company: Case Swot Consulting", Master Thesis in Organization and Management(Unpublished), Department of Marketing and Management, Kelsingin Kauppakorkeakoulu, Helsinki school of economics, Espoo, Finland.

-
32. Mavengere, Nicholas Blessing,(2013b), "Information technology role in supply chain's strategic agility", Int. J. Agile Systems and Management, Vol. 6, No.1.
 33. Vecchiato, Riccardo,(2014), " Creating value through foresight: First-mover advantages and strategic agility", Technological Forecasting & Social.
 34. Tautermann, S. W.& Weichert,S. (2015)," Impact of External Situational Factors on the Agility of Humanitarian Supply Chains: A Case Study of Haiti Earthquake", Master Thesis in Business Administration(Unpublished), Jönköping University, Sweden.
 35. Ivory, Sarah Birrel & Brooks, Simon Bentley,(2017), " Managing Corporate Sustainability with a Paradoxical Lens: Lessons from Strategic Agility", J Bus Ethics (Spring 2017).
 36. Pesonen, Julius,(2010), "Strategy Agility in Production Networks", Master Thesis in Science(Unpublished), Tampere University of Technology.

Difficulties in Mastering English Grammar Faced by Secondary School Students' (Fifth Islamic Grade) from teachers' perspective

Asst. Instructor. Omar Mahmood Mustafa AL-Okiedy
Imam Al-Ghazali High School
Omar8milan8@gmail.com

Abstract: The current study aims to know the difficulties that Iraqi Islamic students face in understanding the English grammar and the obstacles that face the teachers in teaching the grammar in EFL Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5). The sample of the study includes fifteen teachers and the educational supervising (11 boys(56%) and 5 girls(44%))who are actually teaching English in the selected schools during the academic year 2018-2019 (in the Islamic schools) in the city of Kirkuk who represent 61.5 % of the total number of teachers' population. A questionnaire has been conducted and applied to the selected sample. The required data are collected and analysed statistically. The study reaches to results such as , most of EFL teachers are satisfied with the materials of (Book5) concerning their; sufficiency, difficulty, authenticity, integration and appropriacy and the most difficult grammar area is the interrogation and the easiest area is sentence patterns. It also state that the activities and exercises included within(Book5) supply pupils with enough practice in the different kind of English grammar .

Regarding the obstacles of implementation and problems which the teachers face in teaching grammar in (Book 5) are; the present perfect tense is explained briefly in unit two, in some units the subjects of grammar without exercises or activities , shortage of lesson time in some schools,and lack of charts .

Section One Introduction

1.1 Statement of the Problem

English has been chosen as a subject in teaching curriculum of schools. When the students learn English they encounter a lot of problems that might make the process of learning difficult .These difficulties are proper a lot of aspects of differences between two languages. These aspects include syntax, phonology, grammar and morphology(Lado ,1957 :2)

The main purpose of teaching a foreign language is to be able to communicate idea with meanings in the target language (Nasr , 1963 :163) .English as a language based on the skills that are four . They are reading ,writing ,speaking and listening . Each skill sheds light and focuses on different elements of language. One of those elements is grammar.

The grammar teachin g still to b e issues of studying in the side of SLA .It's commonly accept which draws to the structure is good but many research concern the teaching of grammar yet demand studies specifically which are that are certain principle in the learning of classroom (Kennedy ,2001 25).

Al-Mutawa' and Kailani (1989:69) raise that students should understand and produce linguistic forms as part of a purposeful activity, not just as an exercise in language practice.

English course for Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5) for the fifth secondary stage is one the most important variables that affect teaching EFL in Iraq.

English course for Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5) is new considerable curriculum which is taught for the fifth secondary students in Republic of Iraq and yet it hasn't been subjected to any experimental or scientific study . English course for Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5) area those educational courses which are designed especially for foreign language learn in the Islamic Schools.

This study attempts to find the difficulties in mastering English grammar faced by fifth Islamic secondary school Students' .

1.2 Aims of the Study

This study aims to find out difficulties English grammar in EFL Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5) which is taught in the city of Kirkuk for grade five. This aim is supposed to be achieved through answering the following questions:

1. What are the difficulties that Iraqi Islamic students face in understanding the English grammar ?
2. What are the obstacles that face the teachers in teaching the grammar in EFL Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5)?

1.3 Value of the Study

Inserting students to new things would definitely be difficult for them. So when the students learn a new foreign language which is difficult from their native language many problem for the students of this language will seem .

EFL students English grammar (fifth grade) at Iraqi Islamic schools for instance face a problem in understanding grammar in different issues.

EFL English courses texts are new English courses which have been systematically designed to be taught in Iraqi Islamic school. It attempts especially to develop the ability of the four language skills and encourage students to be become confident users of English.

In addition the value of this study could be itemized as follows :

- 1- It concentrate the difficulties faced by Islamic school students in learning English grammar .
- 2- It classifies the problems based on the importance of the contextual difficulties in learning English grammar.
- 3- The results of this study will help educationalists , syllabus designers and decision makers at Sunni Endowment Divan(Religious Teaching and Islamic Studies Directorate),by supplying them with importance information about efficiency of EFL English Course of Iraqi Islamic schools (Book 5).Further , this study could be valuable in reflecting points of view of the fifth secondary schools teachers staff concerning the sufficiency difficult , authenticity and appropriacy of the grammar subjects in (Book 5).

1.4 The Limits of the Study

The current study is limited to English course fo r Iraqi Islamic school (Book 5) and the fifth year secondary teachers and English supervisor in the city of Kirkuk during the year of 2018-2019 .

1.5 The Definitions of Basic Terms

1.5.1 grammar :

It is the science of language, its pronunciation, punctuation, syntax and inflexion (Page et al., 1980:151).

1.5.2 Secondary Stage

It is defined operationally to refer to the stage or level of the study which is started after six years of primary education .It includes six years of studying of six textbooks (English course Book 1, Book 2, Book 3, Book 4, Book 5, Book 6).Grade six is considered the final stage in the secondary school.

1.5.3 English course for Iraqi Islamic Schools

It is also defined operationally to indicate the multi-level course that has been especially designed for secondary Islamic schools .It includes six levels .The first three textbooks (Book1-3) are specified for the three intermediate grades , and the (Book 4 -6) are specified for the three preparatory grades .

1.6 Plan of the Study

The following steps will be followed to be gain the aim for this study :

- 1- Slecting the groups of fifth year secondary teachers from the Islamic schools at Kirkuk.
- 2- Consructing a questionnaire for EFL teachers and English supervisor to show their point of view about English course for Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5) .
- 3- Selecting the sample of teachers and English supervisor,then administrating the constructed questionnaire to the selected sample .
4. Obtaining the results and testifying some conclusions ,recommendations , and suggestions for further work.

Section Two
Theoretical Background
2.1 The concept of English Grammar

Language system is a grammar . By the grammar ,it can be said that , the efection in the exact time of language . The grammar rules inform us why . However, there are about 3,500 rule s in the English (Oxford University Press, 2006).

An infant's implied the grammar information is huge complicated than heaviest model , (Harper, 1999).

Grammar is defined as a description of the structure of a language and the way in which linguistic units such as words and phrases are combined to create sentences in the language. When communication is occurred between sentences and utterances, it used to represent some experiences or describe real and unreal world (Richards and Schmidt ,2002:230).

As for Fromkin et al, (2005:14), the grammar as a term is used with a systematic ambiguity .On one side, the grammar refers to explicit theory which is created by the linguist and proposed as a description of the utterer's competence, and on the other side, it refers to the competence itself as an innate ability of a native speaker. This denotes our linguistic competence of our mother tongue.

By the grammar , it can be means that the rules that done in the early of 17th century and it continued to nowadays (Nasu , 2002 :93).From this , the word can be both single or plural . The foundation of English is rul During the 16th and 17th centuries,English grammar strated to be done spesifically to aid the learning of Latin . (ibid: 94).

2.2 The Kinds of English Grammar
2.2.1 Interrogation in English Grammar

Specialists has been classified the interrogation into many types ,such as :

1)**Y es – N o Question s** : It has many names such as Nexus question or Polar question (Jespersen, 1933:296). Yes – No question occurs when the auxiliary ver b is located before the subject (Are mo , 1997 : 342).

2) **Wh-Questions**, it is also known as{ Information-seeking Questions}. They are formed with one of the followi (Where , why , why ,how and what). For example :

Q1 : Where is the cat A: on the desk .
Q2: when does Ali wake up ? A: At 7 o'clock .

2.2.2 Nouns in English

The noun cab defined easly as a thing and it is thw essence of sentence building . There are a varirty of things nouns such as animal , person .idea etc... The example of noun can be shown in the sentences :

- 1.The baby and daughter were shaking their heads as thy passed our place.
- .2.We like watching T.V at the home

(Quirk and Greenbaum ,1985 :59)

The kinds of Noun

There are many kinds of nouns , they are coomonlt classified about four types (proper ,common nouns and abstract and concrete nouns)

1. Common nouns are the words that refer to things that are universal : umberalla evening bathing
 - We love swimming in the pool
 - The milkcup has been fallen and broken
2. Proper noun s are names of that are specifies someone or something ,such as Ali is a proper noun .
 - Rami loved staying with his uncle Sami in Baghdad .(Jespersen, 1933:152).
3. Concrete nouns refers to the things that is real : smell ,man and soup .
 - The woman throw the stone behind the people
 - Can you tast the soup , Cathy ?
4. An abstract noun refers to the things that is better like an idea or concept .Thre are example of this type :
 - Childhood and beauty are equally
 - Your idea can distinguish many things.

2.2.3 Simple present ,present continuous and present perfect

1.Simple Present

It's form : either by making the verb as base with plural form or by adding s or es to ending of the verb .

Use s :

First use : the habitual action

Example :The sun rises.

Second use : the fact that timeless

Example : The train depart at 7:00 a.m.

(Murphy and Smalzer ,2003 :2-5)

2. Present P erfect

F orm : Subject + Has l h ave + past participle

It occurs in the action tha t happenin g in the p ast , and contioue at the present time

Example : They have broken the window .

(Murphy and Smalzer ,2003 :38)

3. Present Continuous

It's form can be said that auxi. verb that foolwed by the subject is to be (is , are , am) plus verb with ing .It refer to the action that happens now and have not finish yet .

Example : Ali is eating an apple now .

(Jespersen, 1933:230).

2.3 Learning English through Grammar

There are many views in teaching English language from these views ,the approach argues that language exists in context, . The pedagogica l methiod resulting in the style linguistics also search to discover students why language contrast to the situation in that it is made (Nunan, 1991:152).

Swain (1985:50-153) has extra practical mass to that issue ,discovering that pressing to the language objective in context that is meaningful is enough fo all students to grow a complicated grammar knowledge .

Mckay (1987: 154-158) suggests that there are three different opinions on teaching grammar. The first view is that teaching grammar involves these the formal meaningful process of analogy rather than explanation. The learners may become fluent in the structures they have been taught, but may not be able to use them appropriately in wisely communication outside the classroom. The third view is that teaching grammar is a matter of giving learners the chance to use English in a variety of realistic situations.

Frank and Rinvolucri (1987: 98) attempt to offer a kind of classroom exercises and activities, with intensive preparation in a number of basic morph syntactic items, so within a context which tensions "Communicative" rather than "linguistic" competence, and ability rather than knowledge. Therefore, the student control what is said, while the instructor provides way on how it is said. "This adds up to total involvement of learner's whole person, with total responsibility for what he or she produces in a rather loose framework of predetermined cues" (Frank and Rinvoluci, 1987: 7).

Generally speaking, CLT is linked with a shift from traditional form-oriented to a meaning oriented teaching; consistently educators are anticipated to help their learners learn how to voice their notions and illocutions instead of plaguing them with never-ending formal pattern drills; that obviously goes with the slogan that predictable form-and teacher-centered approach should be substituted by a learner centered approach. "say what you mean" instead of "Do as you are told", as well as "fluency above accuracy "(With a correspondingly relaxed view of students' linguistic errors) are other slogans that fit into the general concept of CLT.

Section Three Procedures

3.1 Population and sampling

The population of the study includes the total number of the teachers of English who teach Book 5 at the Islamic schools for boys and girls. These schools are distributed into the city of Kirkuk and its suburbs. In Kirkuk ,there are 20 Islamic school s , 30 for boys and seven fo r girl s. These 20 schools including twenty-six teachers of English .

The sample of this study includes fifteen Islamic schools, eight for boys and seven for girls. After discluding five schools, the sample of the study includes sixteen teachers and the English supervisor (9 boys(56%) and 7 girls(44%))who are actually teaching English in the selected schools during the academic year 2018-2019 who represent 61.5 % of the total number of teachers' population.

Table -1-
The Sample of Study

Num. of boys' teachers	No. of girls' teachers	Total	
9	7	16	
% 56	% 44	% 100	Percentage

3.2 Construction of the Questionnaire

The instrument of this study is a questionnaire. It bases on fourteen item s that includes 5 likerate scale . The selected teachers are asked to rfers their view point belonging the items by (✓) in the suitable place (see appendix A).

3.3 Validity of the Questionnaire

Accoding to the Borg and Gall (1983:173) validity for the questiona re refers to the degree to that a measurement instrument what is obvious to be measuring.

To make the fac e validity of the questioner e, it was showed to juey members of university teaching staff , as shown in the appendix (C)

3.4 The Reliability of the Questionnaire

A questionnaire reliability can be distinguished by researcher of the study on a short sample. It can be also gained by making differences between the answers of the new one with the original one (Best and Kahn, 2006: 329).

To make the questionnaire realibility ,(Person Correlation Formula is applied by making split – half).so the finding of this method is appeared as 0.78 (Carroll and Hall, 1985: 125).

3.5 The Pilot Questionnaire Study

Ther e are a variety intentions that are probably to be accomplished during the form of the pilote study they are :

- Discovering the questionnaire relibability .
- Discovering the obviousness of the items .

The questionnaire was applied to the 15 teachers of English who really taught the EFL English Course Fo r Iraq I Islami c Schhol (Book 5) .

The pilot study has appeared that items that are given are obvious and the time that demand for answering goes through 31 to 41 minutes.

3.6 Final administration of the Questionnaire

The result of questionnaire administration denotes that it i s valid and reliable. T he final questionnaire administration to the study sample has been carried out from 2nd March, 2019 to 24th March 2019. The designed questionnaire which consists of fourteen items is written on a sheet of paper and administrated individually to the selected sample of the teachers. Each teacher is requested to answer to formed questionnaire paper and give it back to the teacher at once .

Section Four

Analysis of Data ,and Discussion of Results, Conclusion ,and Recommendation

4.1 The Percentage of Teachers' Responses on the Constructed Questionnaire

In order to answer questions that are raised in this study, the collected data concerning teachers' points of view about the various items of the constructed questionnaire are interpreted as follows,:

1. The answers of the first and second questions show that; 84% of the teachers think that the grammar of the English course For Iraqi Islamic schools (Book 5) arranged according to difficulty, and 16% of them think the opposite. Moreover, 72% of them think that the exercises of grammar included with (Book 5) reinforce those which have studied within the explained subject , and 28% of them do not think so.
2. Results of the third question show that; 41% of the teachers think that the grammar activities are given with the exercises enough to enhance students learning.
3. Responses on the fourth and fifth questions; 91% of the teachers clarify that the conditional clauses are placed randomly in unit 9 and 9% of them do not think so. Moreover, 77% of them point out that the grammar of (Book 5) supplies students with sufficient opportunities to use English language communicatively and 23% of them think the opposite.
4. Results of the sixth, seventh and eighth questions reveal that; 100% of the teachers believe that the grammar of (Book 5) appropriate for the fifth students' level, 68% of them believe that there are subjects of grammar without exercises such as in unit one (The Future Tense) and 32% of them do not think so, and 95% of them state that the subject of interrogation placed suitably in the (Book 5), while 5% of them have the opposite idea.
5. In the answer of the ninth question: 91% of the teachers believe that students can get enough time and opportunities to understand the tenses intensity especially in the first two units. and 9% of them believe the opposite.
6. In answering the tenth question; 40% of the teachers state that the sentence patterns (in unit 7 and 8)suitable for the fifth students' level and 60% of them think that it does not.
7. In answering the eleventh question; 95% of the teachers indicate that the "Nouns " are explained appropriately in (Book 5), whereas 5% of them do not think so.
8. In the answer of the twelfth question; 100% of the teachers clarify that the present perfect tense is explained briefly in unit two.
9. Result of the thirteenth question that concerning to arrange the subjects of grammar according to difficulty on ten units can be summarized in the following table:

Units	Subjects of grammar	Percentage of Teachers' Responses
one	simple present ,simple past and the future	66 %
Two	present continuous and present perfect	56 %
Three	conditional clauses	58 %
Four	conditional clauses in past perfect tense	76 %
Five	sentence patterns	53 %
Six	nouns	86 %
Seven	question with auxiliary verbs	74 %
Eight	question without auxiliary verbs	66 %
Nine	Yes-No question	67 %
Ten	Wh-question	80 %

10. The last item of the teachers' responses reveal that 80% of the teachers suggest to make the subject of grammars more easy ,Moreover , 90% of teachers clarify their ideas to make connection between the subjects of grammar in (Book 5) and the (Book 6) .

The Final Result of the Mean, Std. Deviation, Percentage of Agreement and Level of Agreement of the Questionnaire

Sample	Mean	Std. Deviation	Percentage of Agreement	Level of Agreement
16	3.9	1.27	82.4	Agree

Note:

In the answer of the note question; 55% of the teachers mention that they have attended in service-teacher training courses and 45% of them has not attended any teacher training course whereas 80% of them have not attended in any workshop that concern their specialist. Moreover, 100 % of teachers mention that they have not participated in any conferences. Most of the sample teachers have the B.A. degree in English language .

4.2 Discussion of the Finding of the Questionnaire

the collected responses on th e items of the questionnaire could be summed up in the following points:

- (Book 5) supplies pupils with sufficient practice in the different subjects of grammar. It has showed that the most difficult area is the subject of interrogation. Also it gives students enough opportunities for practicing different subjects of grammar. (Book 5) materials provide students with authentic information, knowledge about English grammar. It arranged according to difficulty and they include useful and suitable pictures and colours.(Book 5) are available, useful and suitable for given exercises.
- (Book 5) contains clear and easy instructions to be applied in teaching.
- Most of the EFL teachers believe that the subjects of grammar in (Book 5) are clear and attainable for many reasons as follows:
 - a- (Book 5) allows group and individual work. It helps pupils to use English communicatively.
 - b- The course is appropriate for the fifth students' level. It helps students and teachers to speak and communicate, because it is based on communicative approach. Thus, it makes the learners participate in classroom activities. Teachers consider it a practical course.
 - c- (Book 5) gives enough time and opportunities to understand the tenses intensity especially in the first two units.
 - d- This course provides opportunities to practise all the skills and language aspects. It also gives them a lot of chances to practise various language functions.
 - e- In (Book 5) "Nouns " are explained appropriately and suitably.
 - f- It gives more information about different subjects of English grammar.
 - g- It is colourful. It contains nice pictures. Moreover, it is well-organized. This makes the activities interesting and reinforces learning. It also works like a good dictionary.

Most of the teachers need to participate in service-teacher training courses , workshop and conferences (if it is possible). All of them state that there is no mistake in (Book 5). Most of teachers believe that the appropriate number of students should be no more than fifteen in each classroom.

- Regarding the obstacles of implementation and problems which the teachers face in teaching grammar in (Book 5) are; the present perfect tense is explained briefly in unit two, in some units the subjects of grammar without exercises or activities , shortage of lesson time in some schools, and lack of charts .

4.3 Conclusions

The administrated of the questionnaire to the sample of th e current study yielded the conclusions as following g :

1. Most of EFL teachers are satisfied with the materials of (Book5) concerning their; sufficiency, difficulty, authenticity, integration and appropriacy.

- 2- The most difficult grammar area is the interrogation and the easiest area is sentence patterns.
- 3- The activities and exercises included within(Book5) supply pupils with enough practice in the different kind of English grammar .
- 3- The instructions included in the (Book 5) are clear and easy to be applied for teaching the lessons materials.
- 4- (Book 5) supplies students with sufficient opportunities to use English language communicatively. It is appropriate for the fifth students' level.
- 5- Teachers are faced with a lot of obstacles and problems in teaching grammar in(Book 5), i.e. the present perfect tense is explained briefly in unit two, shortage of lesson time in some schools, smallness of classroom size, lack of electricity, and lack of charts .

4.4 Recommendations

A number of recommendations are stated below:

- 1- Supplying teachers with some national as well as international periodical ,journals ,and forums for training them in effective instructional strategies for desired learner outcomes.
- 2- Empowering EFL teachers through professional development and attending in-service training courses, joining support network and national associations, and participating in workshops and conferences.
- 3- EFL teachers should be encouraged to join local and national teachers' associations and pursuing profession development.
- 4- The Sunni Endowment Divan has to enable secondary Islamic schools teachers to meet regularly with well-experienced ones, attend, and observe their lessons and discuss what went on in their classroom. Challenging teaching situations is essential to improve new teachers' teaching practices and English skills.
- 5- Training courses should be continuous for all of the teachers. They need more practice and more information about this new course. Moreover, teachers must be sent abroad for summer courses to improve their language and be acquainted with English culture.
- 6- Substitute those foreign proper names like: John ,Dave Madday, Nelson, ... etc. to others local and familiar names like: Ali , Muhammad, Ahmed, Omer, etc., substitute foreign places' names like: Roma ,Paris, London, to others like : Mecca, Baghdad, Erbil, Cairo, etc..

Bibliography

1. -AL-Mutawa , Najat and Taiseer , Kailani (1989) **Methods of Teaching English to Arab Students**. Longman.
2. -Aremo, B. (2004): **An Introduction to English Sentences (I & II)**. Ibadan: Scribo Pub. Ltd.
3. -Arnoff ,Mark and Ress-Miller, Janie (2003) **The Handbook of Linguistics** . USA :Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
4. -Brown , R. (1968): **Introduction to grammar** , wiley , New York .
5. -Frank, C. and M., Rinvolucru, (1987), **Grammar in Action**, Hemel Hempstead: prentice Hall.
6. -Fromkin,V and Rodmay, R,and Hyams, N. (2005). **Introduction to Language**. (7thed).Thomson Place, Boston, Massachusets.
7. -Good , Carter (1973) **Dictionary of Education** .New York : Mc Graw.Hill Book Company.
8. -Harper, Collins Cobuild (1999) **COBUILD English Grammar (Collins COBUILD Grammar)**. United States : New York
9. -Mckay, S. (1987). **Teaching Grammar: Form, Function and Technique**. Hemel Hempstead: Prentice Hall.
10. -Murphy , Raymond and Smalzer , William R. (2003) **Basic Grammar in Use**. Hong Kong :Cambridge university press.
11. -Nasu , N. (2002): **Aspect of syntax** .phdiss , Essex: Essex university press .
12. -Nordquist, Richard. (2019, January 16). Conditional Clause in Grammar. Retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com/conditional-clause-grammar-1689905>.
13. -Nunan, David, (1989) **Designing tasks for the communicative classroom** Cambridge University press.

14. -Otto, Jespersen (1933) **Essentials Of English Grammar**. Great Britain : George Allen And Unwin Ltd London.
15. -Oxford Practice Grammar(2006) Oxford University Press.
16. -Page , T.G, J.B Thomas and A.R. Marchall (1980) **International Dictionary of Education**. Great Britain :Longman.
17. -Quirk , Randolph and Greenbaum, Sidney (1973) **A University of Grammar of English** . Hong Kong :Longman Group (FE)
18. -Richards, J and Schmidt, R. (2002). **Dictionary of Language and Applied Linguistics**. London: Pearson Education Ltd.
19. -Swain, M. (1985). "Communicative Competence: some roles for comprehensible input and comprehensible output in its development". IS. Gass and C. Madden (Eds) **Input in Second Language Acquisition**, Rowley, Mass: Newbury House.
20. -Ur,P.(1988) **Grammar Practice Activities**. Cambridge University Press.
21. -Wilkins. D.A. (1972). **Linguistics in Language teaching**. Edward Arnold, London.

***Please put (Tick) on the following Schedules**

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Rarely	Strongly Agree	Agree
1. The grammar of the English course For Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5) arranged according to difficulty .					
2. The exercises of grammar included with the English course For Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5) reinforce those which have studied within the explained subject .					
3. The grammar activities are given with the exercises enough to enhance students learning .					
4. The conditional clauses are placed randomly in unit 9 .					
5. The grammar of English course For Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5) supplies students with sufficient opportunities to use English language communicatively.					
6. The grammar of English course For Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5) appropriate for the fifth students' level .					
7. There are subjects of grammar without exercises such as in unit one (The Future Tense) .					
8. The subject of interrogation placed suitably in the English course For Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5).					
9. Students can get enough time and opportunities to understand the tenses intensity especially in the first two units.					
10. The sentence patterns (in unit 7 and 8)suitable for the fifth students' level .					
11. The "Nouns " are explained appropriately in English course For Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5).					
12.The present perfect tense is explained briefly in unit two.					
13. Arrange the following subjects of grammar according to difficulty on the following ten units:					
❖ a. Wh-question					

- ❖ b. Yes-No question
 - ❖ c. question with auxiliary verbs
 - ❖ d. question without auxiliary verbs
 - ❖ e. nouns
 - ❖ f. simple present ,simple past and the future
 - ❖ g. present continuous and present perfect
 - ❖ h. sentence patterns
 - ❖ i. conditional clauses
 - ❖ j. conditional clauses in past perfect tense
- Unit one Unit Two Unit Three Unit Four Unit Five
Unit six Unit Seven Unit Eight Unit Nine Unit Ten

14.If there are any obstacles or problems that you face in teaching the grammar of English course For Iraqi Islamic Schools (Book 5)?**Mention them with further suggestion(if it is available) .**

Appendix (B)

The letter of the Jury Members

Republic of Iraq
Presidency of Sunni Endowment Divan
Religious Teaching and Islamic Studies Directorate
Imam Al-Ghazily Islamic School,

To /

Dear Sir, Mrs.

The researcher is conducting a study entitled "**Difficulties in Mastering English Grammar Faced by Secondary School Students' (Fifth Islamic Grade)**". This study attempts to identify difficulties in English grammar adopted in designing English course For Iraqi Islamic Schools to find out to what extent these difficulties exist.

To fulfill the aims of this study a questionnaire has been constructed. I would be grateful if you, as expert in applied linguistics, pass judgment on the suitability of items, and to decide the face and content validity of the questionnaire.

Any comments, modifications or suggestions would be highly regarded and appreciated. Thank you in advance for your assistance and cooperation.

Yours faithfully
Asst. inst. Omar. M. Mustafa
M.A. in ELT

Appendix (C)

Jury Members

1. Prof. Nahida Taha Majeed (Ph. D. in ELT) College of Education for Human Sciences/Tikrit University .
2. Prof . Amra Ibrahim Sultan,(Ph. D. in ELT) College of Education for Human Sciences/Tikrit University

-
3. Prof .Istabraq Tariq Jawad ,(Ph.D. in ELT) College of Education for Human Sciences/Tikrit University .
 4. Prof. Nagham Qadoori,(Ph.D. in ELT) College of Education for Human Sciences / Tikrit University .
 5. Prof. Shaima Mahdi Saalh ,(Ph.D. in ELT) College of Education for Women/ University of Baghdad.
 6. Asst. Prof. Manal Omer Musa,(Ph.D. in ELT) College of Education for Human Sciences /Tikrit University.
 7. Instructor Ghanim M.Hussein , (M.A. in ELT) College of Basic Education / University of Kirkuk.

INTERPRETATION OF WORKS IN MODERN UZBEK DRAMATURGY IN THE FORM OF THE IMAGE OF CONTEMPORARIES

Qodirjonova Navro‘za Ashirmurodovna
Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture
1- course master

Abstract: In this article, comments are made on the activity of modern Uzbek dramaturgy and the interpretation of images in the works. Also, the processes are widely covered with examples with detailed analytical framework on the shortcomings and achievements that exist in the field.

Keywords: national mentality, aesthetic look, dramaturgy, image interpretation, modern look

Today, the creation of the image of a contemporary hero is a topical issue for our dramaturgy. The article deals with the image of contemporary heroes created by our modern playwrights. In particular, the innovations in the system of aesthetic views of the Uzbek national thinking have had a significant impact on the development of drama today. After O. Yakubov's "Secrets of a House", Usman Azim's "One Step Way", Erkin Samandar's "Arab Muhammad Bahodirkhan", Ilhom Hasan's "A Little World", Abdullah Azam's "Dugohi Husseini", "Jack London" "is one of the achievements of modern Uzbek drama.

Consequently, in U.Azim's drama "One Step Way" such vices as indifference to human desires, disrespect for time are reflected in the complex fate of an old man who worked hard and lived an honest life. An old man and his wife, who had dreamed of visiting Samarkand all their lives, but who did not see the neighboring city due to the shortness of their hands at the time, and then the worries of life, and then the neglect of their children. The psyche of his sons is shown with great skill in the play. At the same time, formal research and creative experiments in the drama of independence did not stop for a moment. Few playwrights, realizing that innumerable life situations could lead to serious changes in the nature of the protagonists in these situations, invented new forms of expression, such as drama-version, drama-situation, which ensured the success of the works. [1; 65]

It should be noted that today, the achievement of national dramatic artistic achievements is a difficult field. The drama of the independence period became the most widely given literary genre to the demands of a market economy. This did not go unnoticed by the quality of the hoi stage productions, of course. It is well known that for our national literature, telling the truth has become a simple requirement of artistic creation. Today, literature is accustomed to the need to express the necessary statement, the current problem in an effective way, linking it to the fate of man. In national drama, it is still a virtue to say the necessary thing in a naked, sharp way. Speaking of modern drama, it should be noted that special attention is paid to the development of this literary genre, which is the basis of theatrical art. Advice is not enough to guide young people in the right direction.

It is necessary to do practical work that will serve the development of goodness, patriotism, human qualities. One such factor of practical education is theater. The theater should bring to the stage works that tell

the story of selfless people who live in harmony with the times, who have been refined in the trials of life. It is necessary to create the image of modern heroes who will strengthen the spiritual world of our children, increase their confidence in the future, strengthen their courage. Therefore, in every sphere of our cultural life there is a unique research on the creation of the image of a modern hero. In particular, the traditional biennial "Let's sing you, contemporary!" As an example, we can say that the Republican Festival has caused a certain shift in our dramaturgy. In preparation for the festival, our playwrights have created a number of new plays depicting modern heroes. In particular, the work "On the Way to Goodness" (Sh. Rizayev), which depicts the creative work going on around us, "Angels in white coats" about the selfless medical workers who dedicated their lives to medicine.

(F. Bobojonova) drama, "Spring wind" (N. Abbaskhan), which reflects the life of young people who invented and cultivated a new variety of cotton, "Other people" (O. Khakimov, S. Odilov) about the life of factory workers, representatives of the fourth power "Swan" (M. Komiljanov), "Paradise Woman" (O. Madatova) about a woman who overcame the hardships of life with her great endurance, "Courage" (H. Khursandov) about the activities of police officers in the border areas, patience, These include dramas such as "You Awaken the Sun" (Q. Norqobil), which sing of endurance, textual will, and devotion to one's spouse in all circumstances. [2; 87] Bold steps are being taken to create a modern hero. In recent years, many works have been written on global issues such as human trafficking, drugs, and terrorism. In this sense, Rixsivoy Muhammadjanov's play "Aydin" (National Academic Drama Theater) is about the problem that plagues the Uzbek child today - human trafficking and its tragic consequences.

The situation in which the protagonist of the drama "Aydin" fell is not simple. In the course of the interview, based on the details of the girls who were trafficked, the protagonist finds out that one of the main culprits for the girls' suffering is his spouse, and the emotional processes that take place in his heart are revealed in a unique setting. It is not surprising that the creation and appearance of works based on such emotional experiences gives each spectator a unique feeling and character. And what exactly is drama in this regard? Dramatic works should ask the question of how the image of the modern hero appears.

As a literary work, drama is interpreted on stage by an actor or director. The great English playwright W. Shakespeare said, "The world is the theater and the people are the actors." Shakespeare believed that drama should obey the law of three units. Unity. 2. Time. 3. Unity of place. Only this requirement can be used to create a good work. [3; 54] Kamil Yashin in the creation of a modern heroic image in dramatic works is one. This school has nurtured and is educating many students of artists, inspiring and inspiring many students to creative heights. At the same time, the influence of the flag bearer of our drama on his fellow writers, the influence of his comrades on him, the influence of each other as teachers and students have their own traditional effects.

Dramaturgy and collegiate plays of our dramaturgy, especially "Gulsara", "Nurkhan", musical dramas are exemplary examples for students and comrades. In the art of moving the characters, these works are

continued by the author and his colleagues, enriching them with new innovative features. In this regard, the play "Alisher Navoi" (1944) by Uygun and Izzat Sultan is especially noteworthy. Each epoch has its own masterpiece, its own masterpiece of the literary process. It is hard to imagine the twenties and thirties of our drama without "The Servant with the Rich", "The Case of Maysara", "Secrets of the Paranja", "Gulsara", "Nurkhan". It is difficult to understand the 1940s without Alisher Navoi. So let's take a look at this play from a dramatic point of view. The names of those who have dedicated their lives to the struggle for the happiness of the people, who gave their lives for the national ideals, are immortal. Immortalizing them in life, as in literature, has always been one of our top priorities. Already in our literature there are historical themes, while the modern one is very important. Because the problem of modernity cannot be solved only by works written from these days.

By referring to history, the writer seeks facts from it that help to solve modern problems, approaches history in terms of modern trends and subordinates it to the service of our time. Our history, rich in unparalleled battle pages, is always close and precious to our contemporaries. [4; 98] Thus, in recent years, Uzbek drama has undergone great changes. It is in the process of creating a modern image of a hero. In the face of the contradictions of life, a number of images were created of people who did not retreat, who sought to understand themselves, and who were able to express themselves. But at the same time, it is too early to say that all the heroes who are still being created are artistically mature, heroes who can withstand the test of time. Nevertheless, the first bold and successful steps give great hope for the future of this work. No matter how complex and multifaceted this process is, there is no doubt that it will yield positive results through the pursuit and pursuit of innovation. The creative principles and methodological researches of Uzbek prose writers of several generations, which create the history of the modern literary process, are analyzed and studied on the basis of the principles of the literary direction called "stream of consciousness". The leading features of artistic methods, such as symbolism, modernism, surrealism, existentialism, provide a basis for thinking about the aesthetic nature.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Happiness of the Free Homeland. Dramaturgy. Five volumes. Prepared by: Sh. Rizayev, T. Islomov. - T.: "Adib". 2013. J. 3.
2. U. Azim. Silence. - T.: "Gafur Gulom". 2012.
3. Madayev O. My lone star. Theater Magazine, 2013. №1.
4. Rizayev O. The image of a modern hero on the stage. Theater Magazine, 2010. №5.

Teenagers Psychology In Young Wrestlers

Bekov Dilshod Haytboyevich
bekovdilshod9@gmail.com

Annotation: The article is about young wrestlers and the tasks and research methods of pedagogical psychology, biological and social factors in personality formation, the relationship between mental development and education. It is intended for university students, as well as educators working with children and students of different ages.

Key words: eacher psychology, teacher's duties, his professional qualities, pedagogical abilities.

Президентимиз Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг жорий йил 15 февралдаги Маданият ва спорт соҳасида бошқарув тизимини янада такомиллаштириш чора тадбирлари тўғрисидаги фармони мамлакатимиз спорти ривожига янги даврни бошлаб берди. Фармонга биноан Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жисмоний тарбия ва спорт давлат қўмитаси ташкил қилинди. Аҳоли кенг қатламини спорт билан шуғулланишга жалб этиш, жисмонан соғлом авлодни тарбиялаш, спорт индустрияси ва инфратузилмасини ривожлантириш, шаҳар ва туманларда оммавий спорт тадбирлари ва мусобақалар ўтказиш, Миллий олимпия қўмитаси, спорт турлари бўйича федерациялар ва ассоциациялар билан биргаликда истедодли спортчиларни танлаш, тайёрлаш ва маҳоратини ошириш, кадрлар тайёрлаш, соҳага замонавий технологияларни жорий этиш ва халқаро алоқаларни кенгайтириш унинг асосий вазифалари этиб белгиланди [1].

Кичик мактаб даври 6-7 ёшдан 9-10 ёшгача давом этади. Бу даврда бола мактаб ўқувчиларига қўйиладиган турли талаблар билан жисмоний машқлар юклагани, босимини ҳис қилишини танишади, кураш асосларини ўрганиш учун биологик ва психологик жиҳатдан тайёрланади. Унинг психикаси билим олишга етадиган даражада ривожланади. Шу ёшдаги бола идрокининг ўткирлиги, равшанлиги, софлиги, аниқлиги, ўзининг қизиқувчанлиги, ишонувчанлиги, хаёлининг ёрқинлиги, хотирасининг кучлилиги, тафаккурининг яққоллиги билан бошқа ёшдаги болалардан ажралиб туради. Мактаб ихтисослиги курашга БЎСМ да ёш курашчилар таълимига тайёрланаётган болада диққат нисбатан узоқ муддатли ва шартли барқарор бўлади [2]. Кичик мактаб ёшидаги курашчи болаларнинг асосий фаолияти ўсиш ва ривожланиш бўлиб қолмай боланинг машғулотга бориши, унинг психологик ривожланиши ва шахсининг шаклланишидаги ўрни ниҳоятда катта. Ёш курашчилар ўқув фаолиятида ўқитувчи раҳбарлигида инсоннинг турли асосий шакллари мазмунини эгаллайди ва инсоний анъаналар асосида ҳаракат қилишни ўрганади [3]. Машғулот фаолиятида бола ўзиродасини ўқув машғулоти мақсадларига эришиш учун машғулот қилдириш керак. Машғулот фаолияти боладан нутқ, диққат, хотира, тасаввур ва тафаккурини керакли даражада ривожланишини талаб этган ҳолда, шуғулланувчи курашчини ривожланиши учун янги шароитларни яратади. Биринчи бор кураш мактабга келган бола ўз атрофдагилари билан психологик жиҳатдан янги муносабат тизимига ўтади. У ҳаётининг тубдан ўзгарганини, унга янги мажбуриятлар, нафақат, ҳар куни ўқув ва тарбиявий машғулотлардан ташқари мактабга бориш, балки кураш машғулотлар фаолияти талабларига бўйсунуш ҳам юклатилганлигини ҳис эта бошлайди. Оила аъзоларининг бола ўқув фаолияти, ютуқлари билан қизиқаётганлиги, шунингдек, машғулотлар жисмоний юклагани яний чарчоқ ва толиқиш назорат қилаётганлиги, унга қилинаётган янги муомала, муносабат унинг ижтимоий мавқеи ўзгарганлигини тўла ҳис этишига, ўзига нисбатан муносабатининг ўзгаришига асос бўлади. [4]. Катталар болаларни амалий жиҳатдан ўз вақтларини тўғри таксимлаш борасида яхши ўқиш, кичик туризм сайирлари ва саёхатлар, сайр қилиш ва бошқа нарсалар билан шуғулланишга ўргатадилар. Демак, оилада бола у билан ҳисоблашадиган, маслаҳатлашадиган янги бир ўринни эгаллайди. Ёш курашчиларнинг мактабдаги муваффақияти унинг кейинги психик ривожига ва шахсининг шаклланишида тўлиқ ижобий асос бўлади. курашчилар 10—11 ёшлардан 14-15 ёшларгача бўлган даврни ташкил этади. Аксарият курашчиларда ўсмирлик ёшига ўтиш асосан, 5-

5. Кичик мактаб ёшидаги курашчиларда нима оркали таълимга бўлган муносабат янада фаол намоён бўлади.

А) Дунёкараш оркали; Б) Кизиқиш оркали; В) Кобилият оркали
Таълим ва тарбия психологиясига бағишланган бўлиб, ўқув фаолиятининг психологик мазмуни ва моҳияти, билимларни ўзлаштиришнинг психологик компонентлари, таълимнинг ноанъанавий усуллари, ўқув фаолиятини ва машғулот дарида ақлни бошқариш психологияси, тарбия психологияси бобида самара беради . Психологик механизмлар, тарбияси кийин болалар психологияси ҳақида батафсил сўз юритилган бўлсада ,

Адабиётлар рўйхати:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2017-йил 15-февралдаги ПФ-4956-сонли фармони
2. М.Г.Давлетшин, Ш.Дўстмухамедова, М.Мавлонов, С.Тўйчиева, М. Джумабаева
3. Гафаров А.З., Югай А.Х. Педагогик амалиёт. Тошкент, 2002
4. Давлетшин М.Г., Тўйчиева С.М. Умумий психология. Тошкент, 2002.
5. Давлетшин М.Г. Замонавий мактаб ўқитувчиси психологияси. Тошкент, 2002.
6. Щербаков А.И. Ёш психологияси ва педагогик психологиядан практикум. Тошкент, 1991.
7. Психология. Қисқача изоҳли луғат. Тошкент, 1998
8. Ғозиев Э.Г. Психология. Тошкент, 1994
9. А.А.Диллоевич, О`збекистонда миллий курашнинг ривожланиш истиқболлари
10. Матвеев Л.К. Массовая физическая культура в ВУЗе (учебное пособие для вузов). М.: Во`сшая школа. 1991.
11. Имомов М.П. “Касб-хунар коллежларида ўқувчиларнинг касбий маданиятини шакллантириш”// Мактаб ва ҳаёт журнали 2012-№2 Б 26-бет
12. Кошбахтиев И.А. Основ физического совершенствования студентов. Учебник для преподавателей и студентов вузов. Т.: 1991.
13. Абдурасулова Г.Б., Нуриддинова Ш.Н., Тажибаев С.С. Таэквондо назарияси ва услубияти. Дарслик. Тошкент – 2015.
14. Глебов Е.И. Таэквондо. Основы олимпийского спарринга /Е.И. Глебов, Чой Сунг Мо. - Ростов-н/Д: Феникс, 2002.
15. Суханов А.В., Фомин Е. В., Булыкина Л.В. Прыгучесть и прыжковая подготовка волейболистов. Методическое пособие. № 10. - М., 2012, - 24с.
16. Беляев А.В., Савин М.В. Волейбол. // Учебник для студентов вузов ФК. М.: ТВТ, 2009. – 368с.
17. Айрапетьянц Л.Р. Волейбол//Учебник для высших учебных заведений. Т.: Zar qalam. 2006. - 240 с.

Formation of legal consciousness among young people

Captain Tursunov Alisher Qahramonovich

Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Teacher of special subjects of Tashkent Academic Lyceum No. 2

Annotation: Formation Of Legal Consciousness In Our Society, Formation Of Legal Consciousness Among Young People And Prevention Of Offenses Between Them, Increasing Legal Culture Serves Understanding The Essence Of Laws.

Key Words: Legal Consciousness, Thinking With Legal Knowledge, Legal Culture, Obedience To The Laws.

Presidential Decree "On the strategy of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the Law "On the dissemination and use of legal information", adopted on September 7, 2017, 2018 - Presidential Decree "On measures to radically improve the activities of judicial bodies and institutions in the implementation of state legal policy" dated April 13, 2019, "On radical improvement of the system of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society" dated January 9, 2019 "The adoption of the Presidential Decree and other normative legal acts" is a confirmation of our opinion. In order to achieve the place of this social category in society, to ensure its place in the minds and thinking of people, we must first of all get acquainted with its scientific analysis and scientific and philosophical roots.

It is correct to say that legal consciousness is one of the foundations of the legal life of civil society, because as one of the forms of social consciousness, the formation and development of legal consciousness is influenced by socio-political, economic, cultural factors. Legal consciousness is a system of knowledge and ideas about the law, the assessment of existing law, the necessary changes in legislation. Legal consciousness also works as a means of influencing the entire legal system of the state. In the process of socialization, a person born in society assimilates the values created by all previous generations, so in the process of historical development of society, legal consciousness is objectified.

Legal consciousness and the legal system formed in any society interact with each other. On the one hand, while legal consciousness develops in accordance with the law, on the other hand, the legal system formed in this society serves as one of the most important factors influencing legal consciousness. In consideration of the structure of legal consciousness, it is generally appropriate to distinguish between ordinary or everyday legal consciousness and theoretical legal consciousness.

We know from the results of many studies that there is a regulation of behavior within the properties of consciousness, and in social consciousness it has taken a separate form, that is, a form of legal consciousness. In particular, a number of researches of Uzbek scientists are focused on this topic. For instance, according to the opinion of Z. Islamov, "Legal consciousness can be defined as a system of legal perceptions, ideas, assessments, perceptions that express the attitude of citizens of the country to the existing law, legal practice, civil rights, freedoms, obligations, as well as the desired law and other legal phenomena.

The study of legal consciousness has been the subject of much research by Russian scientists in the twentieth century, and we may find different views in them. For example, according to Y. Dmitriev: "Legal consciousness is a set of views, ideas, perceptions of people and their various units, as well as society as a whole, in relation to existing legal and legal phenomena. The development of society, according to NM Korkunov, is associated with the ideals of society, and the more developed the ability of society to create ideals, including legal ideals, it will be so advanced. Law is beginning to be understood as one of the highest values of human life.

In his report "Our Parliament must become a real school of democracy, the initiator and main executor of reforms," President Shavkat Mirziyoyev critically analysed the activities of political parties, their parliamentary factions and deputies, and expressed the following views: Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that in order

to improve the work of deputies, increase the legal culture of the population, it would be useful to introduce a new system through political parties: "Center - region - district" because the creation and development of all laws is carried out by deputies. They must be among the people, study all the proposals and recommendations, shortcomings, and create laws based on the interests of the people, the needs of the people. It is no coincidence that the system is a "center-region-district", a change in any policy and to make the people aware that the additions will reach from the center to the province from it to the district and other peripheral areas and that such a system should be created, given that it must convey its views. It is necessary to effectively use the opportunities of communication technologies, social partnership with government agencies.

In order to improve the legal awareness and legal culture of the population in 2019, the Presidential Decree "On radical improvement of the system of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society" was adopted.

The decree states that one of the most important conditions for promoting the rule of law and strengthening the rule of law is to raise legal awareness and legal culture in society.

It should be noted that the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan is in the field of raising legal awareness and legal culture in society.

Delivering and explaining to the public in various forms the legal literature in the information-resource centers and information-library funds, carefully studied by lawyers;

- Establishment of a special legal advocacy center named after the great jurist scholar Marg'inoniy.

Another way to educate the public in the field of law is to increase the number and improve the quality of personnel with higher legal education. To this end, increase the number of higher legal education institutions, train highly qualified lawyers. Let us recall the thoughts of Abu Nasr al-Farabi. The famous philosopher argued that every official should study the laws in depth, be a personal example of their observance, be able to promote the law among the population, make suggestions for its improvement, and, if possible, write a law.

Based on these criteria, in the decrees of the President in 2019 to strengthen the vital idea in the minds of citizens: "Deciding in society the spirit of respect for the law - the key to building a democratic state governed by the rule of law!". One of the primary tasks is to form a system for consistently informing the population about the ongoing socio-economic reforms in the country, the adopted legislation and state programs.

That's why, today the legitimate question arises as to whether we all follow these rules all the time. After all, the norms of the law live and are realized only if they are absorbed into the minds of people and acted through them. And the law is the will of the people.

Thus, the content of legal consciousness is multifaceted, and the rules of the individual's relationship to the law and legal phenomena, society is characterized by the fact that there are many views, a set of ideas that define and reflect their compliance with the norms and principles of justice.

Based on the above, I would like to make the following suggestions.

First, to hold regular roundtables and training seminars or scientific conferences in order to raise the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population;

Second, there are many competitions in the field of law in general secondary education, secondary special vocational education and higher education. Now it is necessary to organize such competitions not only in educational institutions, but also among communities under the name "Leader of Legal Culture". Carrying out competitions and competitions among the regions selected from among the districts;

Thirdly, I think it is necessary to create the Constitution in public places and provide it with modern means of propaganda, reflecting the Constitution and laws, including billboards that will improve the legal awareness of the population and increase the legal culture;

Fourth, raising the level of legal literacy in educational institutions is the most pressing issue, so the legal awareness of the Constitution and human organization of classes and textbooks on the organization of their rights, raising the level of legal knowledge and literacy of young people;

Fifth, changes and additions will be made to the legislation, legal norms. These are not available in old-year law textbooks, so textbooks in all areas of law should be republished in full, continuously, as amended, in large numbers each year;

References:

1. Gulnora Inomjonova. Scientific-practical manual "Marriage contract - a legal guarantee of family stability", -T.: Intellect Expert, 2015, p.
2. Legal maturity leads to perfection "Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan.-T.: Adolat 2011, 7-p
3. Islamov.Z.M. Theory of state and law.-T.: Adolat, 2007.-537-p 413 [Http://OAC.DSMI-QF.UZ](http://OAC.DSMI-QF.UZ)
4. 'Oriental Art and Culture "Scientific-Methodical Journal - (3) III / 2020'Oriental Art and Culture" Scientific-Methodical Journal - (3) III/2020
5. YA Dmitriev. Legal awareness and legal culture / Theory of state and law. Edited by Pigolkin. - Moscow: Yurayt - Publishing, 2006. - P. 547
6. U.Tajikhanov, A, Saidov. Theory of legal culture Volume 1.- Tashkent. 1998, 11-p
7. Approved by the Resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 29.08.1997 No. 466-I.Nrm.uz
8. Legal basis for the protection of the rights and freedoms of the population, the further development of legal consciousness and culture in society. E. Kadyrov // Materials of the round table on the role and place of non-governmental organizations in the protection of the rights and freedoms of the population, raising legal awareness, the formation and development of a culture of human rights in society. - T.: Tashkent Express Publishing House, 2015, p
9. Public Opinion Survey by the Center for Public Opinion Research on the 25th Anniversary of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Kun.uz 24.11.2017
10. Odilkoriyev HT Theory of state and law (textbook). - T.: "Adolat", 2018, 287-p
11. Zakirova Sevara. "The role and place of non-governmental organizations in improving the legal culture of women." // Civil society. 2017, №4, 49-p
12. PF-5618. lex.uz
13. From the information of the Minister of Justice Ruslan Davletov on the promotion of legal advocacy and enlightenment at the fourteenth plenary session of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan // Man and Law, April 3, 2018, № 13
14. Scientific-methodological brochure on the study of the State Program for the implementation of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the Year of Dialogue with the People and Human Interests. - T.: Spirituality, 2017, p. 143
15. Speech by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 27th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. www.Zarnews.uz
16. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On approval of the concept of continuous spiritual education and measures for its implementation" No. 1059, December 31, 2019.nrm.uz
17. Khudoyor Mamatov "Legal consciousness, legal culture determines the development of the state and society" uza.uz
18. Diyorova Shahloxon. "On the factors of developing the legal culture of students of pedagogical universities" // Pedagogy, 2019, №2 134-p.414
19. [HTTP://OAC.DSMI-QF.UZ](http://OAC.DSMI-QF.UZ)
20. 'Oriental Art and Culture" Scientific-Methodical Journal - (3) III/2020 ISSN 2181-063X
21. Abdukamol Rahmonov. "High legal culture - the foundation of a democratic society." // Lawyer, 2019, №1. 8-9-b
22. Protection of the rights and freedoms of the population, the legal basis for further development of legal consciousness and culture in society. E. Kadyrov // Materials of the round table on the role and place of non-governmental organizations in the protection of the rights and freedoms of the population, raising legal awareness, the formation and development of a culture of human rights in society. - T.: Tashkent Express Publishing House, 2015, p
23. Locke J. Works in 3 volumes. Vol. 1. Experience of human understanding. (Philosophical heritage. T.93) .- M.: Mysl, 1985.- 621s-C.3-76.
24. Philosophical Dictionary / Ed. I.T. Frolov. - 4th ed. - M.: Politizdat, 1981. - 445 p.

-
25. Durkheim E. On the division of social labor / Per. with fr. A.B. Hoffman, notes by V.V. Sapova. - M.: Canon, 1996. -- 432 p.
 26. Hegel.G.W.F.Phänomenologie des Geistes. (1807). Berlin-52-p
 27. Islamov.Z.M. Theory of state and law.-T.: Adolat, 2007.-537-p
 28. YA Dmitriev. Legal awareness and legal culture / Theory of state and law. Edited by Pigolkin. - Moscow Yurayt - Publishing, 2006. - P. 547
 29. Kareev N. I. Foundations of Russian sociology. SPb., 1996.S. 123-142.

Psycholinguistic, ethno-sociocultural aspects as basis of intercultural communication

Mavlonova Oybarchin Sheraliyevna

2nd year master's student at the University of World Languages of Uzbekistan

Annotation: This article describes in detail the psycholinguistic, ethno-sociocultural aspects, ethno-sociocultural concepts and the basis of intercultural communication.

Key words: psycholinguistic, ethno-sociocultural, intercultural communication, synthesis," semantic differential".

Psycholinguistics is the study of the origin of speech, as well as the processes of speech perception and improvement in the context of their interaction with the language system; a synthesis of psychology and linguistics. Psycholinguistics develops a model of human speech activity and psychophysiological speech development and analyzes them through psychological experiments. Psycholinguistics, which is close to linguistics in terms of research sources, is close to psychology in its research methods. It uses interrelated experiments, such as "semantic differential" and other experimental methods.

Intercultural communication is the interaction between different cultures, which involves indirect communication between people, as well as indirect forms of communication (language, speech, writing, electronic communication).

We have touched upon the ethnosociocultural characteristics of understanding above, now we will consider more psycholinguistic aspects of understanding. According to R. Penrose, consciousness is continued in the intellect. Operating unit of understanding is the code that has a symbolic nature: "Symbol is always something that we do not fully understand, but what we are as someone who understand, who exist". Thus, from our point of view, the understanding and consciousness operate with one and the same instrument – symbol.

Intercultural communication is essentially interpersonal communication in a special situation in which one participant recognizes the cultural differences of another. Such communication raises many issues related to the different hopes and beliefs that are unique to each person in different cultures.

The act of communication cannot take place if the message is not encoded: "Code is a key concept in intercultural communication...a message should be coded, i.e., to be expressed by the code and decoded, i.e. be understood...thus the encoding in intercultural communication is the conversion of the first signal system to another by using the internal (the "language of thought") and external (verbal and non-verbal forms) codes. Cultural and language codes depend on the national picture of the world".

There are lots of great works about consciousness from the philosophical, psychological, socio-cultural points of view, in this article we will touch upon only two facts of consciousness:

- 1) consciousness is social by its nature, it arose in the process of collective human existence, reflection of reality;
- 2) consciousness has a communicative nature (as a consequence of socialization of the individual), which is reflected in the word consciousness, i.e. a joint knowledge that can be passed to the recipient by means of words, signs, or other visual images, charts, gestures, facial expressions, etc.

Research in language psychology or psycholinguistics has helped scientists better understand the mental aspects of language and speech. Thanks to psycholinguistics, we have new and innovative ways of approaching education.

Intercultural communication is based on the process of symbolic interaction between individuals and groups in which cultural differences are visible. Acceptance and response to these differences affect the appearance, form, and outcome of communication. In addition to cultural differences, the process of intercultural communication is influenced by the age, gender, occupation, and social status of the communicators, as well as their patience, resilience, and personal experience. So, intercultural

communication is the interaction between different cultures. Intercultural communication The fact that the act of communication belongs to different cultures means that the two participants understand each other.

First of all, it is important to determine that psycholinguistics originates from two specific disciplines: psychology and linguistics. The first studies people's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors, while the second studies language and its manifestations.

Both of these fields are combined to study human language. However, psycholinguistics is only the sum of its parts. Instead, he uses theories and approaches in both areas, as well as learning new things. Although other sciences study language, they study it from a different perspective. For example, sociolinguistics studies the interrelationship of socio-cultural and linguistic phenomena. Linguistics itself studies the origin, development, and structure of language.

As a result understanding in intercultural communication can be characterized by the two key aspects: psycholinguistic and ethnosociocultural.

It is important to notice the contingency, synergy of two concepts: understanding and cognition, the latter as a step to understanding, and to constitute the epistemological nature of understanding: "The initial form of spiritual needs in the ontogenetic development seems to be delivered in the functional necessity for self-orientation and cognitive activity, also in the need for external impressions, and never the material needs for food, clothing and shelter".

Understanding is the reflection of higher spiritual need, at the same time it is possible to understand only those things that have been previously cognized and now are known to an individual, without the latter understanding cannot exist (even an emotional response in the soul can be caused only by those phenomena that were previously understood or experienced by the individual). According to Rene Descartes, the understanding is identified with cognition, intelligence, and thinking, and in its turn, implicitly includes what is now usually called consciousness. We can build the following chain of cognitive processes: perception (rational or irrational, i.e., feeling) – cognition – understanding – consciousness.

Ethnosociocultural concepts take place in different language systems or in a single social language. That is, they consist of concepts that reflect human behavior in a field of activity, in particular, elements that contain information. In summary, we can say that a concept is a unity of consciousness. In conclusion, we can say that the concept is the unity of consciousness. No matter what situation a person lives in, there is always an element that motivates him to develop an understanding of a concept. And man's interests in this field further expand or narrow the conceptual sphere in his mind. This field, which is currently of great interest and development in world linguistics, has not yet been fully explored, and not even dictionaries have been compiled to explain the essence of the concept. A broader and more detailed coverage of this issue awaits its researchers in the future.

References:

1. Averincev S.S., Davydov Y.N., Turbin V.N. et al. (1992). M.M. Bakhtin as a Philosopher. Coll. Papers Inst. of Philos. RAS. M.: Nauka.
2. Humboldt V. (1985). Language and Philosophy of Culture. M.: Academic prospect. P.346 – 350.
3. Clarke R. B. & Campbell D. T. A demonstration of bias in estimates of Negro ability // Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology. Vol 51. 1955. –P. 58-588.
4. Judith Martin, Thomas Nakayama. Intercultural communication in contexts. —5th ed. –New York: McGraw-Hill, 2010. -528 p.

The concept of heroism and its representation in the novel “The Old Man and The Sea”

Name: Sobirova Nurkhon Barot kizi

Work place: Bukhara State University

Position: Teacher at the “English literature and stylistics” department

Abstract: With the only word “hero”, a plethora of personages who make people or even the whole world astonished strike our minds in the blink of an eye. But there are such unique figures of the literature to whom worldly attention does not make any sense or the absence of millions of “eyes” is unable to hinder their heroic deeds. This can vividly be shown with the example of the fisherman Santiago in “The Old Man and The Sea” by Ernest Hemingway. “A man can be destroyed but not defeated” a statement made by the real hero-writer of the twentieth century whose epoch-making symbolic quotation echoes the invincible spirit of a hero who reaches the zenith of his success ultimately. In my study, I make an effort to find and analyze clear illustrations for the notion of heroism and represent it with the characters of the novel.

Key words: Heroism, parallel suffering, dignity

Introduction

“Literature is the writing or the study of books etc. Value as works of art” (Hornby et al, 1973: 572). Literature is not anything that is written. That is to say, pamphlets, brochures, textbooks, leaflets are not considered to be literature. Literature has something special to delivery and represents life. The characters, the conflicts, the setting presented in the story are realistic that makes the readers suspicious it as if it were true event in life. However, the readers must be aware of the fact that there is sharp discrepancy between the world of real life and that of literary work. The world within a work of literature is fictional. The same point is also true for the novel “The old man and the sea” by Ernest Hemingway. The setting can be real but the struggle of human being and natural forces is filled with shades of fictional “pencil”. The concept of heroism is described in this work such a beautiful way that it is impossible to ignore it with the image of different characters and the themes of the work which is illustrated below in detail in the discussion part. Research method is also followed by introductory part. At the end, to summon up all the points, concluding part is also addressed.

Research Method

The object of the study is the novel entitled *The Old Man and The Sea* first published by Ernest Hemingway and was then published by Charles Scribner's Sons in 1952. The novel consist of 48 pages. The formal object of this study, research involves there is main issues Heroism reflected in Ernest Hemingway’s *The Old Man and The Sea* (1952). The data of the research are the text in Heroism reflected in Ernest Hemingway’s *The Old Man and The Sea* (1952). The data source is divided into two categories: primary data sources and secondary data sources. The primary data are taken from Heroism reflected in Ernest Hemingway’s *The Old Man and The Sea* (1952). The secondary data includes some information that will support the research on the novel *The Old Man and The Sea*. This kind of data will be criticisms on *The Old Man and The Sea*, other studies that have been done related to the novel, and study guide in Hemingway’s work.

The technique used to collect the data is documentation technique that tries to collect data from the written records (books, articles, archives, etc.) that are related to the problem (Moleong, 1990: 113-114, 131). The next phase after collecting data is analyzing the data. Method of analysis used in this research is descriptive with evaluation and interpretation. Descriptive analysis is an explanation of the relation between the data (Moleong, 1990: 6). The last step then, is drawing a conclusion to answer the problem, which has been stated on the objective of the research. The conclusion derives from the explanation of the pattern from the descriptive codes and the general idea of it.

Discussion

Hemingway's heroes make a breakthrough in the connotation and transcend the traditional function of heroes (Alik Alhakamul Khusna, 2018:15p.). Many of the characters in Hemingway's novels and stories are called heroes because they still preserve some of the virtues of the romanticized figures and the noble people in the traditional sense – bravery, courage, faith, perseverance, dignity, etc. These heroes are more human than divine, more complex than simple. The virtues Hemingway's heroes show when facing the harsh reality serve not as models for people to follow but purely as the revelation of the consolation and comfort for the bitter agony and pains. Hemingway's heroes are not always strong-minded, tough, sturdy, but rather dualized (Khusna 2018).

Animated and Restrained

Hemingway's heroes are both animated as well as restrained, and seem to possess great spiritual energy. His works capture the extremes of heroism and tragedy. His heroes convey a sense of grandeur and power, and arouse strong emotion. In size, strength and emotional intensity; these characters go beyond the real people. The novel *The old man and the sea* describes the adventure of a single fisherman, highlighting his hard work, and his hard earned prize, the huge marlin, which at last, falls prey to the hungry sharks. Hemingway himself as a war correspondent, also praised the heroism of the man's long silent struggle with the earth and the elements. Hemingway's story begins most lyrically describing most the personal feeling instead of the acts of heroism portrayed in the epic struggle of the old man and with the huge fish. The story begins depicting the interaction between the primary characters as they prepare their fishing gear for the following day near a Gulf Stream harbour in the 1940s.

Santiago as the representator of heroism

Santiago as a protagonist, his actions, activities, life style as well as his close similarity to the author, expression how Santiago grows matures from an old damaged man into a true hero by not give up his attitude to life. *The Old Man and the Sea* is, from one viewpoint, an interpretation of Hemingway's personal struggle, unattractive, definite, resolute and everlasting, to write his best. With his seriousness, importance, his correctness and his perfectionism, Hemingway saw his abilities correctly as Santiago. "(TOMDS:P:2-3)".

Parallel Suffering

For ordinary reader it appears to be like that Santiago as a main character has to suffer from struggles but what about other characters? Marlin for example? Meanwhile, the old man is also suffering from fatigue and he begins to experience faintness and dizziness, the marlin has also weakened though. Yet, Santiago refuses to break down their physically or mentally, and continues working his great marlin closer to the skiff. Finally the marlin circles close enough for the old man to spear it with his harpoon which he drives in with all the strength he can send for.

Energetic and Controlled

Hemingway's heroes are both energetic as well as controlled, and give the impression to own great spiritual transcendent liveliness energy. His heroes deliver a sense of dignity, majesty and power, and produce strong emotion. In dimensions, strength, responsive and emotional concentration; these personal characters go beyond the real people. The novel "*The old man and the sea*" designates the exploration adventure of a single fisherman, importance his hard work, and his hard received award, the enormous Marlin, which at last, decreases target to the hungry sharks.

The Dignity

The authority and Dignity of Hemingway's novels are resonant through the novel. The introductory profile is of Santiago, and „Old Man“ in the title, and the main character, through the story section, essentially speaking, he is portrayed as the hero of the novel. But as heroic his bear huge Marlin, Santiago calls him his „brother“. He is a Cuban fisherman, described and designated as being old in every technique except his eyes, which “were the same color as the sea and were cheerful and undefeated?. Even though

Santiago has not caught a fish for eighty four days, he overlooks the hisses and disappointment of other fishermen and revenues to the sea in his skiff day after day. The old man's sail was "patched with flour sacks and. furlled it looked like the flag of permanent defeat"

Patience

From the beginning of the work, the novel is constructed under the quality of patience and endurance. The survival fight receipts its climax, the obstinate marlin drawn the line unkindly and quickly, till it has cut Santiago's face, his body was so tired, and his hand was numb and impractical, even with all this bodily weaknesses, the old man was coming up for the right time to harpoon it, as shown below. Once the fish, made a surge that pulled him down on his face and made a cut below his eye. From time to while Santiago was talking to his enemy (the marlin), he asked the fish in unintended way to transporting under his leadership, "If you're not tired, fish, he said aloud, you must be very strange". He felt very tired now and he knew the night would come soon and he tried to think of other things. "(TOMAS, p. 05)".

Individuality

Not considering his only companion Manolin, Santiago's life is left in isolation. Santiago's life is categorically heroic typical, the old man all through his day; he creates his detailed selections of what he precisely lives for, and what he can live without. Santiago was struggling in life to endure with his dignity and independence, without admiration of what he movable, or in what he be unsuccessful; the main point that distinguishes Santiago from the other fishermen and people in his rural community is his high level of consciousness and desire of his skill. To be specific for Santiago is not just to be by you and isolated from people, but be specifically in a world full of differences and departures.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of the whole paper, this study comes to the following conclusion. Firstly, there are Ernest Hemingway's novel *The Old Man and the Sea* is one of the great fictional works. For sure, it transports the message meaning of human existence way of life and dignity. The old fisherman measured by many people who read to be a tragic hero, in that his greatest strength principals to him to subsequent collapse. In this study, the researcher is concerned for the Heroism in the novel *The Old Man and The Sea* as a character the clarification and unravels it by using the approach.

References

1. Hornby et al, 1973: 572. Literature the study of books published by Charles Scribner's Sons in 1952. *The Old Man and the Sea* is a novel by Ernest Hemingway
2. (Barker, 2004). the changeable character of social formations whose core features are located in the material conditions of existence.
3. Robert P. Weeks, "Hemingway and the Uses of Isolation," *University of Kansas City Review*, XXIV, 125 (Winter, 1957).
4. E. M. Halliday, "Hemingway's Ambiguity: Symbolism and Irony," *American Literature*, XXVIII, 3 (March, 1956).

Review Of the Issue of Faith (Iman) In the Works of Hakim Tirmidhi

Zafar Fakhridinov,

Basic doctoral student of the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
Tel: (93) 505-59-96 mobile. z.fahriddinov@iiu.uz 11, A.Qadiri, Tashkent, 100011, Uzbekistan.

Abstract: It is not known whether Hakim Tirmidhi wrote a work in which he reflected his sectarian and doctrinal views separately. However, there are records in the sources about his treatises being written as a rebuttal to various sects. The Egyptian scholar Muhammad Juyushi, who has studied the legacy of the scholar in detail, also draws attention to this issue and points out that although al-Hakim al-Tirmidhi did not write an independent work on Kalam, the author's denials to the various sects from the point of view of the Ahl as-Sunnah reflects on some of the shortcomings of the Rafidhis' beliefs, such as "ar-Radd alar-Rafidha" and "ar-Radd alal-Muattila," which were written as a refutation of the Mu'attila sect¹.

Key words: Hakim Tirmidhi, Egyptian scholar

It is not known whether Hakim Tirmidhi wrote a work in which he reflected his sectarian and doctrinal views separately. However, there are records in the sources about his treatises being written as a rebuttal to various sects. The Egyptian scholar Muhammad Juyushi, who has studied the legacy of the scholar in detail, also draws attention to this issue and points out that although al-Hakim al-Tirmidhi did not write an independent work on Kalam, the author's denials to the various sects from the point of view of the Ahl as-Sunnah reflects on some of the shortcomings of the Rafidhis' beliefs, such as "ar-Radd alar-Rafidha" and "ar-Radd alal-Muattila," which were written as a refutation of the Mu'attila sect².

Abu al-Hasan al-Hujwiri (d. 466/1073 or 470/1077) wrote in his "Kashfu-l-mahjub": Al-Hakim studied fiqh in the hands of one of Abu Hanifa's special companions³. Ibn Arabi (560 / 1165-638 / 1240) also confirms this information of al-Hujwiri, mentioning in his work "al-Futuhatu-l-Makkiyya" that Hakim al-Tirmidhi was of the Hanafi school⁴. It can be said that Hakim Tirmidhi was of the Hanafi school of thought according to the phrases he used. In particular, in the beginning of "Buduvvu-sh-sha'n" the author writes about himself that he has compiled "ilmul-asar and ilmur-ra'y"⁵. The phrase "ilmul-asar" reflects the science of hadith and is usually expressed by the word "asar" in the works of the first Hanafi scholars. "Ilmu-r-ray" means the science of ijihad and fiqh in the broadest sense, and the rational method of the Hanafi school in the narrow sense. Usually, the people of hadith do not deal with "opinion".

It can also be seen from Hakim al-Tirmidhi's views on fiqh and aqeedah that he belonged to the Hanafi school. In particular, his "Bayanul-Farq" describes faith as follows:

"Faith is the affirmation of the Truth in the eyes of the scholars and according to the Shari'ah - the acceptance of the heart and the affirmation of the tongue⁶. Faith is not as imperfect as the sun, but just as sunlight is less when it is cloudy, foggy, hot or very cold in the air, so is the light of faith diminished for some reason"⁷.

¹ Al-Juyushi M. Al-Hakim at-Termizi Muhammad ibn Ali - dirāsaton li-āsārihi and afkārihi. Cairo: Doru-n-nahzati-l-arabiya, 181.

² Al-Juyushi M. Al-Hakim at-Termizi Muhammad ibn Ali - dirāsaton li-āsārihi and afkārihi. Cairo: Doru-n-nahzati-l-arabiya, 181.

³ Al-Hujwiri, Abu-l-Hasan Ali ibn Uthman al-Ghaznavi. Kashfu-l-mahjub. V. Zhukovsky, who prepared the scientific-critical text for publication. Leningrad: GAT, 1926 - B.178.

⁴ See Usmanov I. The influence of al-Hakim al-Termizi's teachings on the views of Ibn al-'Arabi // Lessons of Imam al-Bukhari. - Tashkent, 4 / 2003.- B. 183-186.

⁵ At-Tirmidhi al-Hakim, Muhammad ibn Ali. Tarj. J.Cho'tmatov. Tashkent: Movarounnahr, 2018.- B. 26.

⁶ At-Tirmidhi al-Hakim, Muhammad ibn Ali. Bayānu-l-farq bayna-s-sadr and-l-qalb and-l-fuād and-l-lubb. Prepared by Yusuf Walid Mariy. Ammon: Muassasatu Āli-l-bayt lil-fikr al-islamiy, 2009. - B. 44.

⁷ At-Tirmidhi al-Hakim, Muhammad ibn Ali. Bayānu-l-farq bayna-s-sadr and-l-qalb and-l-fuād and-l-lubb. Prepared by Yusuf Walid Mariy. Ammon: Muassasatu Āli-l-bayt lil-fikr al-islamiy, 2009. - B. 60.

The above description of Hakim al-Tirmidhi is in full accordance with the belief of Imam Azam Abu Hanifa in "al-Fiqh al-Akbar" about the conditions of faith⁸. It should be noted that this was not in line with the beliefs of the Shafi'is and Ahl al-Hadith that existed in the region at that time. Hakim Tirmidhi also stated in his works that he did not openly agree with some of their approaches and even criticized their style⁹.

The issue of faith is also mentioned in Hakim Tirmidhi's dictionary of religious texts, more precisely in the dictionary of the Qur'an "Tahsil nazairi-l-Qur'an" (Study of the meaningful words of the Qur'an). Although al-Hakim al-Tirmidhi in his "Bayanu-l-Farq" mentions the condition of "confession" in accordance with al-Fiqh al-Akbar on the issue of faith, it is clear from his words that affirmation is primary. In "Tahsil Nazairi-l-Qur'an", he also points out that faith is a confirmation:

*"When it comes to the word of faith [in the Qur'an], it is as follows: "Its commentary has been included in the previous chapter. Indeed, here faith becomes affirmation. Because affirmation is the work of the soul. Indeed, the slave confirms once he finds peace and stability. Understanding the essence of stability and peace is a confirmation of that.""*¹⁰

Indeed, according to the doctrine of Maturidiyya, faith is the affirmation itself. In fact, confession with the tongue is also a necessary condition for a believer to be judged as a believer in this world, rather than as a direct pillar of faith, even though it is part of the deed. That is, a believer's faith is manifested in his confession, and he is treated according to that confession in Shari'ah matters. According to the confession, there are Shari'ah obligations and rights in matters such as eating, keeping clean, and marrying. The same approach is reflected in Imam Maturidi's masterpiece on theology, "Kitabu-t-Tawhid":

*"Then it became clear from the evidence of the Qur'an and what the believers agreed on and what came out of the tongue that faith is the confirmation.""*¹¹

If we compare the the above-mentioned views of Hakim al-Tirmidhi on faith with the views of Imam Maturidi, there is no doubt that he belonged to the Hanafi school. In addition, Hakim Tirmidhi cited a number of verses as evidence of his views, proving that faith is a feeling that comes from the heart. For example, it is stated in Surah al-Hujurat, verse 7 of the Qur'an:

"But Allah has endeared faith to you, making it appealing in your hearts"

This phrase is interpreted as follows: "Truly, He has made [faith] loving with love and adorned it with wisdom"¹².

It can be seen from the fact that Hakim al-Tirmidhi stated that faith is affirmation, and affirmation is "fi'lul-qalb" - the work of the soul, which he did not consider to be part of faith. At the same time, he emphasized that faith is a feeling that is felt through the senses and understood through the mind. The emphasis on reason in the coverage of doctrinal issues in the works of the scholar is also a clear example of the harmony with Imam Maturidi and the teachings of Maturidiyya. According to Maturidiyya, it is obligatory to know Allah, but the reason is the means by which knowledge is obligatory. In particular, in the introduction to his tafsir "Ta'wilat Ahl al-Sunnah", Imam Maturidi says:

*"It is obligatory for an intelligent child to know Allah, and Allah, glory unto Him, created human beings in a nature that recognizes His Oneness and Rububiyah with the minds they possess.""*¹³

The above sentences show that there is a regular harmony in the ideological views of Hakim Tirmidhi and Imam Maturidi. The fact that reason is one of the obligatory conditions of faith is directly related to the doctrinal views of Imam A'zam Abu Hanifa. Imam Abu al-Barakat al-Nasafi, a follower of

⁸ See Abu Hanifa Nu'man. Al-Fiqh al-Akbar / Translation by S.M. Altynkhan Torah. - T.: Adolat, 2003. - B. 52.

⁹ For more information see: Usmanov I., Fakhridinov Z. vab. Introduction to Sufism. Tashkent: UzXIA, 2019. 48-52.

¹⁰ At-Tirmidhi al-Hakim, Muhammad ibn Ali. Tahsil nazāiri-l-Qur'ān. Prepared by H.Zaydon. Cairo: Matbaatu-s-saada, 1970.- B. 125.

¹¹ Al-Maturidi, Abu Mansur Muhammad ibn Mahmud as-Samarkandi. Kitābu-t-tawhid. Prepared by B.Topoglu, M.Aruchi. Istanbul-Bayrut: Irshod, Doru Sodir 2001. - B. 426.

¹² At-Tirmidhi al-Hakim, Muhammad ibn Ali. Tahsil nazāiri-l-Qur'ān. Prepared by H.Zaydon. Cairo: Matbaatu-s-saāda, 1970. - p. 124.

¹³ Al-Maturidi, Abu Mansur Muhammad ibn Mahmud as-Samarkandi. 1 / Ta'vilāt ahli-s-sunna. Prepared by M.Bāsallum. Bayrut: Dāru-l-kutubi-l-ilmiya, 2005. - B. 176.

Imam al-Maturidi, in his tafsir entitled "Madarik", which is highly regarded in the Hanafi school, citing examples from the words of Abu Hanifa. One of them says:

"Even if God had not sent a prophet, it would have been obligatory for the people to know Him with their minds."¹⁴

It is clear that the intellect is the main means of enlightenment and the formation of faith, which has been firmly established from the time the Hanafi School was formed. Seeing the mind and the narration as equal is one of the basic features of the doctrine of Maturidiya, and this approach is directly related to the verses of the Qur'an, authentic hadiths, and the practice of the caliph Rashid. Verse 10 of Surah al-Mulk has the same meaning:

And they will say, "If only we had been listening or reasoning, we would not be among the companions of the Blaze."

In the above verse, the verb "heard" (nasma'u) refers to naqli evidence, and the verb "used his mind" (na'qilu) refers to aqli evidence. That is, the style of rationality, known in ancient times as "ra'y is directly derived from and based on the sacred sources of Islam. This shows that some ignorant sects today deny the place of reason in religion and claim that "reliance on reason is the style of the Mu'tazilites." In other words, the in-depth study and promotion of the works of both scholars is also important in revealing the enlightened nature of Islam and in the spiritual struggle against various fanatical groups.

Although there is no mention of the country's mutakallim scholars in Hakim Tirmidhi's surviving works, the cited and many other examples embody Hakim Tirmidhi as a scholar who is in harmony with the Hanafi-Maturidi creed. From this it can be concluded that even if the Hanafis in Mawarannahr carried out separate scientific activities, their intellectual and ideological views developed harmoniously.

Summarizing all of the above, we can draw the following conclusions:

- Hakim al-Tirmidhi's attitude to the hadiths differed sharply from that of the muhaddithin because he belonged to the "Ahl al-Ra'y";

- Hakim Tirmidhi and Imam Maturidi were representatives of the same *madhab* in terms of doctrine and jurisprudence. Hakim Tirmidhi's theoretical approaches and views were based on the Hanafi school;

- A number of classical Islamic sources confirm that Hakim Tirmidhi was a Hanafi. Although only Tajuddin Subki (d. 1370) mentions that Hakim Tirmidhi belonged to the Shafi'i *madhab*, it can be said that this situation was most likely the result of confusion¹⁵;

- The analysis of Hakim Tirmidhi's works shows that his doctrinal views are in harmony with the views of Imam Maturidi;

- Hakim Tirmidhi's position on the selection of jurisprudence and hadiths is more in line with the approach of the faqihs than with the hadith scholars. In this respect, it is safe to say that both scholars were like-minded, sympathetic, and of the same *madhab*.

References:

1. Abu Hanifa Nu'man. Al-Fiqh al-Akbar / Translation by S.M. Altynkhan Tora. - T.: Adolat, 2003. - B. 52.
2. al-Hindi, Muhammad ibn Abdulhaq al-Hanafi. Al-Iklil 'alā Madāriki-t-Tanzil and haqaiqu-t-tawil. Bayrut: Dāru-l-kutubi-l-ilmiya, 1971. - B. 310.
3. Al-Hujwiri, Abu-l-Hasan Ali ibn Uthman al-Ghaznavi. Kashfu-l-mahjub. V. Zhukovsky, who prepared the scientific-critical text for publication. Leningrad: GAT, 1926 - B.178.
4. Al-Juyushi M. Al-Hakim at-Termizi Muhammad ibn Ali - dirāsatu li-āsārihi and afkārihi. Cairo: Doru-n-nahzati-l-arabiya, 181.
5. Al-Maturidi, Abu Mansur Muhammad ibn Mahmud as-Samarkandi. 1 / Ta'vilāt ahli-s-sunna. Prepared by M.Bāsallum. Bayrut: Dāru-l-kutubi-l-ilmiya, 2005. - B. 176.
6. Al-Maturidi, Abu Mansur Muhammad ibn Mahmud as-Samarkandi. Kitābu-t-tawhid. Prepared by B.Topoglu, M.Aruchi. Istanbul-Bayrut: Irshod, Doru Sodir 2001. - B. 426.

¹⁴ See al-Hindi, Muhammad ibn Abdulhaq al-Hanafi. Al-Iklil 'alā Madāriki-t-Tanzil and haqaiqu-t-tawil. Bayrut: Dāru-l-kutubi-l-ilmiya, 1971. - B. 310.

¹⁵ See Tajuddin as-Subki. Tabaqātu-sh-shāfi'iyya al-kubrā. 6 volumes / Prepared for publication by Mustafa Ahmad Ata. - Bayrut: Dāru-l-kutubi-l-ilmiya, 1999. T. I. - B. 449.

7. At-Tirmidhi al-Hakim, Muhammad ibn Ali. Bayānu-l-farq bayna-s-sadr and-l-qalb and-l-fuād and-l-lubb. Prepared by Yusuf Walid Mariy. Ammon: Muassasatu Āli-l-bayt lil-fikr al-islamiy, 2009. - B. 44.
8. At-Tirmidhi al-Hakim, Muhammad ibn Ali. Tahsil nazāiri-l-Qur'ān. Prepared by H.Zaydon. Cairo: Matbaatu-s-saada, 1970.– B. 125.
9. At-Tirmidhi al-Hakim, Muhammad ibn Ali. Tarj. J.Cho'tmatov. Tashkent: Movarounnahr, 2018.– B. 26.
10. Tajuddin as-Subki. Tabaqātu-sh-shāfi'iyya al-kubrā. 6 volumes / Prepared for publication by Mustafa Ahmad Ata. - Bayrut: Dāru-l-kutubi-l-ilmiya, 1999. T. I. - B. 449.
11. Usmanov I. The influence of al-Hakim al-Termizi's teachings on the views of Ibn al-'Arabi // Lessons of Imam al-Bukhari. - Tashkent, 4 / 2003.– B. 183-186.
12. Usmanov I., Fakhriddinov Z. & others. Introduction to Sufism. Tashkent: IIAU, 2019. 48-52.